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Project acronym: HIT2GAP

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Research and Innovation Action

Topic: EeB-07-2015 New tools and methodologies to reduce the gap between predicted and actual energy performances at the level of buildings and blocks of buildings

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Duration: 48 months

D7.4 – Dissemination and Awareness Activities Period covered M1-M48

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Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	✓
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the dissemination and awareness activities conducted by the HIT2GAP project partners according to the marketing strategies planned in Work Package 7 and defined in Deliverable 7.2 – “Marketing Communication Strategy”. The report describes in detail these activities in the next sections as follows, organized in categories:

- Section 2 – Introduces the overall **marketing and dissemination strategy** followed aligned with the scientific objectives of HIT2GAP;
- Section 3 – **Market Diffusion** activities focuses on describing market-oriented activities carried out by the project partners. Updated information regarding National Stakeholders Forums is reported in this section. Additionally, EU events and R&D dissemination and awareness activities are also described;
- Section 4 - **Scientific Diffusion** activities deals with (1) Scientific peer reviewed journal publications planned, submitted or published by the HIT2GAP project partners and (2) Conference Communications (Conference Papers, Poster Presentation, Short Communication);
- Section 5 – **Social Media** Communications describes activity metrics and estimated reach of social media instruments such as Flipboard, LinkedIn groups or Twitter. Mass media (TV, Radio) and other communications are also included;
- Section 6 – **Compendium** summarizes the activities carried out by the consortium members alongside with estimated audience reach, as an abridged account of the HIT2GAP dissemination efforts till date.

From the beginning of the project to the end of the project (M48), a significant effort on Dissemination & Awareness activities have been undertaken by the consortium partners, this is summarized as follows:

- HIT2GAP partners have conducted a total of 95 Dissemination and Awareness activities;
- National stakeholder forums are being established in 7 countries with several participations in promotional actions;
- Scientific dissemination of HIT2GAP was reflected in 8 submitted Journal papers and 22 participations in peer reviewed conferences. Among others, HIT2GAP has been presented in the prestigious Building Simulation Conference “BS2017 San Francisco” organized by IBPSA (<http://www.buildingsimulation2017.org/>);
- Regarding social media, HIT2GAP is being disseminated through the HIT2GAP web page which has been redesigned and includes downloadable material. The HIT2GAP Flipboard, Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram accounts are active and helping resonate HIT2GAP efforts to wider audiences;
- During the last period of the project, a specific effort has been made to communicate towards potential end-users/clients of the solution and also to possible contributors (modules developers, open source projects working on a similar topic). This has been done through different means of communication: creation of dedicated website for the BEMServer solution (<https://www.bemserver.org/>) and a video detailing the concept of the solution (<https://youtu.be/fbamTkjYq50>), participation in BIM World 2019 exhibition, local stakeholders meetings inviting clients-to-be, targeted discussions with potential customers and direct commercial action.

1 Introduction

HIT2GAP overall objective is to provide a platform that links key enabling technologies, services and approaches used at the operational stage of the building lifecycle in order to narrow the gap between predicted (whereas by design, or by simulation) and actual measured energy performance of buildings. HIT2GAP develops around the provision of an integrative IT platform following a plug-and-play approach. This platform incorporates innovative IT services provided by large system providers and small to medium innovative start-ups services focusing at enhancing and leveraging existing proprietary Building Management Systems functionalities.

1.1 Reporting periods

This deliverable was periodically updated during the life of the project according with the project reporting periods as listed in Table 1. For each update period, both planned and carried out activities were added, updated, or amended comprehensively from the whole project duration till date. The current report adds to D7.4 the dissemination results from Reporting Period 3 - Month 37 to Month 48- hence represents the total dissemination efforts of the whole consortium for the whole project duration.

Table 1 - D7.4 Reporting Periods

	Reporting Period	Dates Covered	Submission Date
D7.4 – RP0 (initial)	M1 – M12	Sep 15 – Aug 16	31 st August 2016
D7.4 – RP1	M1 – M18	Sep 15 – Feb 17	28 th February 2017
D7.4 – RP2	M19 – M36	Sep 15 – Aug 18	31 st August 2018
D7.4 – RP3	M37 – M48	Sep 15 – Aug 19	31st August 2019

1.2 Dissemination and awareness strategy

The communication objectives and dissemination strategy of HIT2GAP were described in deliverable D7.2 “Market Communication Strategy”. The aim of this strategy is to overcome typical shortcomings when it comes to real dissemination of research and development projects, industry buy-in and user adoption of energy-related innovative project outcomes. Marketing and communication instruments ensure that HIT2GAP foreground is adequately explained to the relevant stakeholders reaching the targeted audience.

HIT2GAP communicates its innovations and novel services using a variety of instruments, from social media to scientific papers. At an early stage, the project partners have used the HIT2GAP webpage and newsletter as the main shared communication exchange tool. Public communication materials (Logo, Website, Flyer, Newsletter and Standard Presentation) have been produced and made available to the whole consortium, as reported in deliverable D7.2 - “Public Communication Materials”. During the life of the project, outcomes are being disseminated using specific high impact scientific journal publications and conference participations. As soon as pilot implementations become ready (WP5) and HIT2GAP modules are validated, communication actions shift towards demonstration events and industry targeted workshops where HIT2GAP foreground can better reach key industry players, government bodies, and other relevant stakeholders.

In D7.2 a number of significant aspects concerning the marketing strategy were defined in accordance with the overall HIT2GAP intentions and challenges identified (see D7.2 document for deeper detail), these will be taken into account in this deliverable:

- **HIT2GAP Audiences**, identifies audience type based on impact, influence “on” or “by” the project and potential uptake of project results;
- **HIT2GAP Key Messages**, sets the relevant messages to be delivered to specific audiences;
- **HIT2GAP Communicators**, analyses the role of specific people participating in the project with regards to delivering key messages using different communication channels;
- **HIT2GAP Methods of Communication** enumerates the available communication channels;
- **HIT2GAP Communication Activities and Measurable Outcomes**, classifies the communication activities according with the Objective, Message type, Frequency, Audience and Communicator agent.

In the following sections, the D&A actions performed by the project partners are described. For each action, the relevant performance metrics are disclosed and the relevant HIT2GAP project outcomes or highlights communicated are also mentioned as keywords.

2 Market diffusion activities

In this section, Market oriented dissemination and awareness activities are reported. This section encompasses all communications targeted at **Industry groups, Government Agencies, Professional bodies**, and other non-academic scientific activities. Mass media and social media communication efforts are **excluded** from this section.

In addition to these events, partners of the HIT2GAP project is seeking the incorporation within the following innovation networks:

- [SECARTYS](http://gici.eu/sites/default/files/gici/public/content-files/pages/CATALOGOSOLUCIONES-GICI_Feb18.pdf) innovation network. HIT2GAP is included in the catalogue with solutions for smart cities that the Smart Cities Inter-Platform Working Group, an initiative of the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness. See link below pages 78 and 79. http://gici.eu/sites/default/files/gici/public/content-files/pages/CATALOGOSOLUCIONES-GICI_Feb18.pdf
- [INNORADAR](https://www.innoradar.eu/innovator/989729801) is an EC initiative to identify high potential innovations and innovators in EU-funded research and innovation projects. ENERIT requested the HIT2GAP energy management module as innovation within the network, which is visible in the below link <https://www.innoradar.eu/innovator/989729801>.

As expected, the last year of the project was intense with regards with dissemination of the project outcomes, as the modules are taking shape and can be shown to potential interested parties. Promotional materials have been updated during RP3: a BEMServer logo, a poster and a leaflet have been produced using the graphic charter of BEMServer also defined during RP3 (Annex3, §9).

2.1 National Stakeholders Forums (NSFs)

The following is a summary of D&A activities carried out at a country level by the National Stakeholder Forums (NSF) in the project partners EU member states. The NSFs are composed of representatives of national and local government, professional bodies, agencies, industry and local businesses. The NSFs provide support to the project at a country level and also represents the interest of the country and its key industry sector with regards to HIT2GAP outputs and potential project adoption. The NSF formation process was described in Deliverable D7.2 – Appendix 1: EU Project HIT2GAP: National Stakeholder Forum.

2.1.1 France NSF

Contact point	Pascale BRASSIER (NBK)	pbrassier@nobatek.com
Partners	NBK, BES, LIU, EVL	
Email list size	About 30 stakeholders in the field of Facility Management, BMS domain, Energy Management, Building management tools and IHM development	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting – 02/02/2016	The first meeting was conducted in the frame of the Innovation Workshop organised by PROMODUL with

	<p>2nd Meeting – 22nd March 2017</p>	<p>French actors such as Trend, Schneider Electric, VELUX, VINCI Construction, Saint Gobain.</p> <p>Conducted at the event “<i>La data Science au service de la Performance Energétique des bâtiments tertiaires</i>” hosted by DARWIN ECOSYSTEMs in Bordeaux. Feedback from the audience was collected in the minutes regarding key questions on building occupant behaviour, measurements needed, BIM use, reliability and customization of the tool and many other aspects in face to face discussions.</p>
<p>Figure 1: French National Stakeholder Forum met at Evolution’s Darwin Ecosystem building – 22nd March 2017</p>		
	<p>30th June 2017 H2020 HIT2GAP: Stakeholder Liaison Group webinar</p>	<p>A teleconference with international stakeholders was held on 30 June 2017. This teleconference involved partners from HIT2GAP, including R2M, NOBATEK and BRE, plus external participants, including representatives from Promodul and Università Politecnica delle Marche (UNIVPM). HIT2GAP partners introduced the external partners to the principles behind the project, including the roles of the various partners, the key modules and proposed business models. Different business models were discussed, including B2B and B2C and options for promoting the project and raising market awareness were also discussed.</p>
<p>Participants provided useful comments and feedback, including the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In practice, comfort parameters are specified by building users, therefore comfort comes before energy. The demands stipulated by the user, however, might affect our definition of the 'gap'. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The main end users are considered to be building owners, facilities managers, ESCOs, EE consultants and BMS providers. • Openware does not always fit well with ESCOs and our exploitation plans might need to be adapted to take account of this. • Market leaders will be reluctant to engage with a shared data system, but some companies other than market leaders might be more willing to accept a system of this type. • Collecting data is expensive because of the cost of the data collection equipment. For this reason, we might wish to limit the number of data input parameters. • National stakeholder groups could benefit from more input from facilities managers.
<p>02nd and 03rd April 2019 Launch of the BEMServer solution during the BIM World 2019</p>	
	<p>Following this event, targeted discussions with potential customers/partners have been conducted (open source project in the same field (Bricks project), VINCI FACILITIES, GA Smart Building, ECOMÉ, OCCITALINE, Kocliko, OPENERGY, SURYA Consultants, OPINUM)</p>

2.1.2 Ireland NSF

Contact point	Luis M. Blanes Restoy	hit2gap-ireland@googlegroups.com
Partners	NUIG – ZUT – CYL – ENE	
Email list size	50 mail list subscribers	
Meetings held	<p>Initial Meeting 13 March 2017 – Conference Call Proposed 2 events to disseminate HIT2GAP. Created HIT2GAP google groups Ireland</p>	
	<p>2nd. Meeting – 21st March 2019 – Alice Perry Building Partner R2M, UoS, Cylon and Zutec met with NUIG Building and Estates to present BEMServer and the planned final testing of modules in the Alice Perry building.</p>	

3rd. Meeting – 29th August 2019 – Alice Perry Building
 Partners R2M, UoS, Cylon and Zutec, Enerit met with NUIG Building and Estates to present findings of the HIT2GAP modules on the selected rooms of the Alice Perry Building. Post-project plans for continuing exploiting HIT2GAP outputs were discussed.

Final Event – 29th August 2019 – Alice Perry Building
 Below agenda of the event. This was broadcasted and included a final panel discussion. Video recording will be available in HIT2GAP website and disseminated in social media (currently in edition).

- Introduction. **Marcus M. Keane (NUIG)**
- Tour of the Building
- Presentations:
 1. Pilot Activities in HIT2GAP & BEM Server. **Tom Messervey (R2M);**
 2. BMS solution and open platforms. **Paul Cowling (Cylon);**
 3. BIM tools and BMS empowering. **Brendan O’Riordan & Liam Stanley (Zutec);**
 4. Dealing with IEQ issues in existing building. **Daniel Costola (University of Strathclyde);**
 5. ModSCO. Easy tool for energy models. **Luis M. Blanes (NUIG);**
 6. BEMServer FDD-PCA. **Marco Pietrobon (R2M);**
 7. Energy Management tool and case studies. **John Cunningham (Enerit);**
 8. Lessons Learned from the HIT2GAP case studies. **Daniel Costola (University of Strathclyde);**
- Open Panel Discussion
- Refreshments

2.1.3 Spain NSF

Contact point	Gorka Naveran	gorka.naveran@veolia.com
Partners	GIR-TEK-EUR-UDG	

Email list size	16 mail list subscribers
Meetings held	<p>01 July 2017, HIT2GAP partners reached out to a potential stakeholder in Spain, Altuna y Uria which is a construction company based in the Basque Country. The remit of Altuna y Uria is relatively broad - they are developers, builders and producers/providers and therefore could include a solution such as HIT2GAP as part of their business offerings. During the meeting with Altuna y Uria, HIT2GAP's IK4-Tekniker presented the project and explained their own contribution to it. This raised various discussions including some that were specially related to the TRL (Technology Readiness Level) of the HIT2GAP solution and the current state of the project.</p> <p>26/10/2017 Bilbao Jornadas de la eficiencia energética “Hacia la clasificación”. VEOLIA. Conference, Spain. This conference aimed at energy service companies and potential customers of these companies. Experts from the associated companies explained the savings achieved in their most emblematic projects in the field of energy efficiency. In this conference, the HIT2GAP project was explained, as an example of what is being advanced in innovative platforms.</p> <div data-bbox="580 976 1286 1496" data-label="Image"> </div> <p>Figure 2: Jose Alonso Urquijo speaks in the Efficiency conference</p>

19-21/01/18 Durango, Spain Berdeago Energy, Feria Vasca de la Eficiencia Energética. VEOLIA. Exhibition. Berdeago Energy is an exhibition showing the latest developments related to energy efficiency in building, bioconstruction, sustainable mobility and waste treatment. This national event brings together all kind of agents related to sustainability

Figure 3: Berdeago Energy Exhibition

15/05/17 Giroa-Veolia facilities, Zamudio, Spain Presentation in Veolia's "Open door day". VEOLIA. Presentation of Giroa-Veolia with teachers and students of EHU/UPV (University of the Basque Country) where the benefits of the R&D projects were presented. Special emphasis was placed on the HIT2GAP project, as attendees showed interest in learning about the latest advances in the behaviour model and monitoring.

Figure 4: Gorka Naveran speaking about HIT2GAP

	<p>15/06/17 Calahorra Hospital, La Rioja, Spain HIT2GAP Presentation for Calahorra Hospital. VEOLIA Meeting between R&D department and the Commercial Director of Veolia with the Central services managers of the Calahorra Hospital (La Rioja, Spain).</p>
	<p>17/01/2018 Projects presentation to VEOLIA clients (IMQ group). Giroa - Veolia organised a meeting with one of his clients (IMQ group). IMQ is an insurance group in the health sector that offers its services in its own medical centres. This meeting was focused on reinforcing its commitment to energy efficiency and reducing consumption in buildings, showing the benefits of HIT2GAP project and presenting its future objectives in achieving the implementation of improvements in the Nanogune pilot site.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Figure 5: Introducing the R&D projects to IMQ group</p>
	<p>6-8/06/2018 Santander, Spain. Projects presentation in “XII Jornadas de Innovación en Servicios Generales Hospitalarios”. VEOLIA. Exhibition. Giroa-Veolia attended the XII Conference of Innovation in General Hospital Services that focused on management of the hospital services and the sanitary assistance in general. The conference took place from 6th to 8th June 2018 in Santander, Spain. Giroa-Veolia introduced the HIT2GAP as an innovative solution that can be suitable for such types of buildings as hospitals and similar healthcare facilities have a huge energy consumption. The HIT2GAP platform can optimize and regulate the energy use with the different modules.</p>
	<p>13/06/2019 Final Spanish Stakeholders workshop HIT2GAP Project was presented in Nanogune, one of the demo cases of the project. The aim of this presentation was to show the benefits and results of the Project to all the attendees, in addition to a visit to the facilities of Nanogune where the developments are being implemented.</p>

Around 15 customers of GIROA-VEOLIA attended the event and among them a responsible for the city of Bilbao and Zarautz, technology center staff, manufacturers, responsible for energy efficiency...

Figure 6: Final stakeholders workshop conducted in NANOGUNE (Spain)

2.1.4 Poland NSF

Contact point	Julius Zach	J.Zach@mostostal.waw.pl
Partners	MOS - WRS	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting 24 May 2017	A meeting took place with the Managing Director in Poland of International Business Contracts to discuss HIT2GAP modules and potential platform capabilities against other solutions.
	Final event 28/08/2019 Final stakeholders workshop	Błażej Rudzki of HIT2GAP's partner Mostostal presented the BEMServer solution for intelligent buildings to an audience of about 60 people at the XII Facility & Property Management conference in Warsaw on 28 th August 2019 where the audience included a mixture of property owners, facility managers, property managers, developers, energy managers and architects. Attendees were given an overview of the BEMServer data platform

		and an introduction to a range of modules that sit on the platform to enable facility managers, engineers and other stakeholders to reduce the energy gap in buildings between actual energy use and projected energy use. The presentation included a description of the pilot building in Wilanow, which has been used to trial the BEMServer energy-saving solution.
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2.1.5 UK NSF

Contact point	Lory McElroy	hit2gap@bre.co.uk
Partners	BRE, UoS	
Email list size	12 (excluding the project team)	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting – 16 Aug 2016	A stakeholder meeting was held at the BRE Innovation Park in Ravenscraig on 16 August 2016. Presentations were given by BRE and UoS, followed by discussions where attendees were asked to consider a number of questions relevant to HIT2GAP. Post-occupancy evaluation, second tier trial buildings and adventitious electrical loads due to building occupiers were all discussed.
	Meeting 1 – 19 April 2017	A stakeholder meeting took place in April 2017 in East Kilbride. The meeting included discussions of some of the HIT2GAP modules that are being developed.
	Meeting 2 – 29 th August 2019	UK stakeholders were given a link to the live stream of the final meeting in Galway on 29 August 2019

2.1.6 Germany NSF

Contact point	Nicolas Rehault	Nicolas.Rehault@ise.fraunhofer.de
Partners	FISE	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting – 3 May 2017	Fraunhofer ISE has run the German NSF. Their first meeting took place the 3 rd May 2017 in Berlin at the Berliner Energietage.

	Meeting 1 – 28 June 2018	Workshop conducted at Fraunhofer ISE the 28 June 2018 in Frankfurt titled "Digital Change - Opportunities for Business Management in the Operation of Facilities of the Technical Building Equipment (TGA) "
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2.1.7 Italy NSF

Contact point	Gianluca Signore	gianluca.signore@r2msolution.com
Partners	R2M – ABO	
Email list size	About 50	
Meetings held	Initial Meeting - 24 January 2017	The meeting took place at the Politecnico di Milano and presented the HIT2GAP and QUANTUM projects to stakeholders illustrating how buildings can benefit from the project outputs.
<p data-bbox="539 1812 1374 1843">Figure 7: Italian National Stakeholder Meeting held in Milan - 24 January 2017</p>		

2.2 Market Dissemination and Awareness Activities

2.2.1 Dissemination and awareness activities performed from the beginning till the end of the project [M1-M48]

The abbreviations used for action type and audience type are listed in annex 1 and annex 2.

Name	Workshop SmarTABCD			01
Action type	WS-AC, WS-I			
Location	Biarritz-Anglet-Bayonne, France.	Date	14/09/2015	
Partners	NBK, FISE, API, R2M, NUIG, UOS, TEC, ENE, UDG			
Link	http://aiai2015.sigappfr.org/			
Description	SmarTABCD'15 Workshop on Smart Technologies and Applications on Buildings, Cities and Districts, Bayonne Château-Neuf (France), International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Application and Innovations (AIAI'15)			
Audience type	I-SW, HEI	Reach	100	
Key Messages	<p>Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to the researchers and industrials that are participating in this workshop.</p> <p>The HIT2GAP partners presented the tools they bring into the HIT2GAP project.</p> <p>Present and Discuss:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Routing Protocol for Wireless Multimedia Sensor Networks - Model Occupant Satisfaction and Behavior in a Building - Energy Management Decision Making - City Scale Modeling - Data Driven Platform for Energy Efficiency Monitoring 			
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables			

Name	PROJET EUROPEEN DE RECHERCHE, HIT2GAP MET L'INTELLIGENCE ARTIFICIELLE AU CŒUR DES BATIMENTS			02
Action type	ARTICLE			
Location	France	Date	17/09/2015	
Partners	NBK			
Link	https://www.batiactu.com/edito/intelligence-artificielle-au-service-performance-energetique-42141.php			
Description	Article describing the project and its main objectives			
Audience type	I-BMS, I-SW, I-ESCO	Reach	250	

Key Messages	Overall description of projects, innovations and ambitions
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables

Name	Sustainable Places 2015	03
Action type	CONF	
Location	Savona, Italy	Date 18/09/2015
Partners	R2M	
Link	http://sustainable-places.eu/past-events/sp-2015/	
Description	Sustainable Places 2015 builds on the two previous successful events in 2013 and 2014. This third edition was an original initiative from the RESILIENT and PERFORMER FP7 European project consortiums, aiming to generate a successful, sustainable and world-class series of annual conferences. Sustainable Places 2015 aimed to gather scientists, researchers, and engineers, from research institutes and the industry, around one of the greatest challenges that our societies have ever faced: ensuring long-term environmental sustainability of ever-growing, densifying urban areas, in a resource-constrained world.	
Audience type	I-SW, HEI	Reach 50
Key Messages	Overall description of projects, innovations and ambitions	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables	

Name	3 rd Innovation Workshop organised by PROMODUL	04
Action type	WS-I, INEF4	
Location	Paris, France	Date 02/02/2016
Partners	NBK	
Link	http://www.cercle-promodul.fr/	
Description	As a founder member of INEF4 (Factor 4 National Innovation & Excellence Institute), the Cercle Promodul Association has implemented some working groups entitled "Innovation Workshops". These workshops are reserved for industrial members of the Cercle Promodul and enable discussions with projects managers leading INEF4 and H2020 projects and therefore benefit from the last R&D developments.	
Audience type	I-BMS, PB-CM, PB-BS	Reach 10
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach and discuss with industrials and specifically with BMS providers.	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables	

Name	Seminaire expert sur la Mesure de la Performance Energetique des Batiments (MPEB)	05
Action type	SEM	

Location	Louveciennes, France	Date	10/02/2016
Partners	NBK		
Link	http://www.batiment-energie.org/index.php?p=37		
Description	Presentation of HIT2GAP at expert seminar dedicated to Buildings Energy Performance Management. Organised by the FEB (Fondation Bâtiment Energie).		
Audience type	PB, G-N, I-BMS, I-SW, I-ESCO, PB-EN, PB-CM, PB-BS, P-FM, EU-H2020, RI	Reach	40
Key Messages	Disseminate HIT2GAP Approach		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables		

Name	Ecobuild	06	
Action type	EXH, CONF		
Location	London, UK	Date	8/03/2016
Partners	BRE		
Link	http://ecobuild.co.uk		
Description	Exhibition and conference used to raise awareness of HIT2GAP project within the construction industry at this 3-days event, which focusses on innovations in construction. BRE used its exhibition stand and speaker slots to do this.		
Audience type	All	Reach	800
Key Messages	Disseminate HIT2GAP Approach		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables		

Name	EeB Impact Workshop	07	
Action type	EU-EEB		
Location	Brussels, BE	Date	19/04/2016
Partners	R2M		
Link	http://ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm?pg=events&eventcode=726793D4-9B63-B6E2-A5C2649F019492E3		
Description	The EeB Impact Workshop is organised by the European Commission with the EeB PPP project representatives. The focus this year is again on generating impact, exploiting synergies and clustering the potential of projects which belong to the same area of research and innovation.		
Audience type	EU-H2020	Reach	50
Key Messages	Disseminate HIT2GAP Approach		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables		

Name	4 th Industrial Technologies Conference			08
Action type	CONF			
Location	Amsterdam, Netherlands	Date	22/06/2016	
Partners	R2M			
Link	http://www.industrialtechnologies2016.eu/			
Description	European Conference held in the RAI in Amsterdam promoting the field of new production technologies, materials, nanotechnology and digitisation. It is the largest of its kind in Europe with more than 12,500 delegates, held over three days.			
Audience type	I-BMS, I-SW, I-ESCO	Reach	500	
Key Messages	Overall presentation of projects, innovations and potential benefits for users.			
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables			

Name	Sustainable Places 2016			09
Action type	CONF			
Location	Anglet, France	Date	29/06/2016	
Partners	NBK, R2M, NUIG			
Link	http://www.sustainableplaces.eu/previous/sp2016/			
Description	Sustainable Places 2016 aims to gather scientists, researchers, and engineers, from research institutes and the industry, around one of the greatest challenges that our societies have ever faced: ensuring the long-term environmental sustainability of ever-growing, densifying urban areas, in a resource-constrained world. A workshop has been organized during the conference gathering the sister projects of HIT2GAP: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TOPAs (coord. MOTOROLA Solutions) - QUANTUM (coord. IGS) - MOEEBIUS (coord. TECNALIA) 			
Audience type	EU-H2020, PP	Reach	50	
Key Messages	Overall description of projects and solutions			
	Identification of possible exploitation route for the project alone or jointly among sister projects			
	HIT2GAP, TOPAs, QUANTUM & MOEEBIUS projects: New tools to reduce the energy performances gap. Four European H2020 funded projects, HIT2GAP, TOPAs, QUANTUM and MOEEBIUS, will work to provide new tools and methodologies to minimise the gap between the predicted and the actual energy usage in buildings and blocks of buildings. The workshop aims at initiating clustering around this topic and discussing the solutions developed as part of the projects.			
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables WP6 due to exploitation synergies. Whole project and clustering strategy			

Name	EESAP 2016			10
Action type	CONF			
Location	San Sebastian, Spain	Date	04/07/2016	
Partners	NBK			
Link	http://eesap.eu/index.php/en/presentation-2/previous-editions/			
Description	EESAP is a European conference on energy efficiency and sustainability in architecture and planning/urbanism. A poster related to the HIT2GAP approach and the envisioned platform has been presented during the conference.			
Audience type	PP, G-N, G-EN, HEI, PB-AR, PB-CM	Reach	25	
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to the research and education groups of the Basque Government, as well as other national and international institutions related to the fields of the climate change, energy efficiency and environmental sustainability			
	Present building energy efficiency solution applied in the project			
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project focusing on the functional platform architecture.			

Name	Cities of the Future			11
Action type	H2020			
Location	Istanbul, Turkey	Date	30/09/2016	
Partners	EGE			
Link	https://www.b2match.eu/futurecities-h2020			
Description	Poster presentation of HIT2GAP at the “Cities of the Future Brokerage Event” in Istanbul which is co-financed by European Union and TUBİTAK.			
Audience type	EU-H2020, HEI	Reach	300	
Key Messages	Overall presentation of the project, innovations and potential benefits for users.			
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables;			

Name	SBE 2016 Istanbul			12
Action type	CONF			
Location	Istanbul, Turkey	Date	13-15/10/2016	
Partners	EGE			
Link	http://www.sbeistanbul.com/			
Description	Presentation of the paper “A Methodology to Develop a User-Behaviour Tool to Optimize Building Users’ Comfort and Energy Use”			
Audience type	PB-AR, PB-ENG, HEI	Reach	50	

Key Messages	Overall presentation of the project, innovations and potential benefits for users.
	User behaviour as key factor on energy efficiency
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables;

Name	MEDES '16 (8 th International Conference on Management of Digital EcoSystems)	13
Action type	CONF	
Location	Hendaye, France	Date 02-03-04/11/2016
Partners	NBK, LIU	
Link	http://medes.sigappfr.org/16/	
Description	<p>The International Conference on Management of Digital EcoSystems (MEDES), previously named "The International Conference on Management of Emergent Digital EcoSystems", aims to develop and bring together a diverse community from academia, research laboratories and industry interested in exploring the manifold challenges and issues related to web technologies and resource management of Digital Ecosystems and how current approaches and technologies can be evolved and adapted to this end.</p> <p>The HIT2GAP project has been presented during the special session on Smart Grids and Smart buildings.</p> <p>Presentation Title: "<i>Hit2Gap - Towards a Collaborative Smart Building Management System Solution</i>".</p>	
Audience type	PP, HEI, PB-EN, PB-IT, PB-BS	Reach 80
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to the research and education groups of the Basque Government, as well as other national and international institutions related to the fields of the climate change, energy efficiency and environmental sustainability	
	Present the HIT2GAP solution applied in the project	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project focusing on the functional platform architecture.	

Name	ISA BTP Business Forum	14
Action type	EDU	
Location	Anglet, France	Date 10/11/2016
Partners	NBK	
Link	http://isabtp.univ-pau.fr/fr/actualites/archives-2016-2017/novembre/les-20-ans-de-l-isa-btp.html	
Description	NOBATEK presented the on-going work conducted within the HIT2GAP project at Higher Institute of building and Civil Engineering of Aquitaine.	

	This event marked the 20 th year celebration event of the ISA BTP business forum.		
Audience type	HEI	Reach	30
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach.		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Flyer distribution.		

Name	EINSTEIN – HIT2GAP Workshop	15
Action type	WS-AC	
Location	Galway, Ireland	Date 14/11/2016
Partners	NUIG, ZUT, CYL	
Link	http://www.einstein-iapp.eu/news https://www.iesve.com/discoveries/blog/2nd-einstein-workshop-ies-building-operations-research-update/	
Description	<p>The second EINSTEIN project workshop was hosted at the Engineering Building at the National University of Ireland Galway last Monday 14th November. The workshop, kindly hosted by the College of Engineering and Informatics (CoEI), provided an opportunity for our building operations team to engage with building stakeholders, students, researchers and external companies, in order to showcase current work and identify opportunities for collaboration.</p> <p>The workshop opened with a tour of the state-of-the-art engineering building at NUI Galway, led by Mr. Aodh Dalton (Chief Technical Officer, College of Engineering and Informatics). Attendees from NUIG-IRUSE, Trinity College Dublin (TCD), IES, Cylon Controls, and ZuTec, were given a guided tour of the building labs, lecture theatres and dedicated energy centre.</p>	
Audience type	PP, RI, HEI	Reach 20
Key Messages	<p>Showcase of HIT2GAP and opportunity for cross collaboration at academic, and industry-academia levels.</p> <p>Stakeholders feedback and information collaboration resulted in a fruitful engagement with NUIG Buildings Office and Facility Managers with views of implementing optimised smart solutions coming from HIT2GAP;</p> <p>Presentation of “The Battle of Buildings”, a NUIG Strategy sustainability awareness and participative project and opportunities to showcase and exploit HIT2GAP outputs through the whole academic community.</p>	
HIT2GAP connection	WP5 – Demonstration in NEB Irish Pilot; WP7 – Stakeholders feedback; Task 1.6 Display Modules, Task 2.4 and Task 3.4 on Building Simulation	

Name	7 th ECTP conference 2016-Innovative Built Environment	16
Action type	CONF, EU-EEB	
Location	Brussels, Belgium	Date 17-18/11/2016
Partners	NBK	

Link	https://fr.xing-events.com/ECTPConference2016.html		
Description	<p>The 7th ECTP conference is organized by the European Construction Technology Platform (ECTP). This event is dedicated to present and discuss current and anticipated innovation in the built environment field (including the issue of energy efficiency of buildings).</p> <p>During the conference, a hall was dedicated to booths and posters that exhibited examples of innovation expected from European projects. This exhibition gave us the opportunity to present the HIT2GAP solution together with two other innovative products coming from H2020 projects: BUILT2SPEC and E2VENT.</p>		
Audience type	PP, PB, G-EN, RFA, FI, HEI, EU-H2020	Reach	200
Key Messages	<p>Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach, find synergies and share experience with other projects.</p> <p>Present the HIT2GAP innovative solution developed in the project</p>		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project: context, objectives and developed solutions.		

Name	BAUSIM 2016	17	
Action type	CONF, EU-EEB		
Location	Dresden (Germany)	Date	14-16/09/2016
Partners	FISE		
Link	http://www.ibpsa.org/bausim-2016/		
Description	Participation in the BAUSIM 2016 conference presenting the paper "DENSITY-BASED CLUSTERING ALGORITHM FOR FAULT DETECTION AND IDENTIFICATION IN HVAC SYSTEMS "		
Audience type	HEI - REI	Reach	20
Key Messages	Present the HIT2GAP innovative solution developed in the project		
HIT2GAP connection	WP2 and WP 3		

Name	Meeting with ALDI Nord supermarkets	18	
Action type	UPEV		
Location	Girona, Spain	Date	17/01/2017
Partners	UDG		
Link	N/A		
Description	Individual meeting with a service sector customer		
Audience type	CON	Reach	5
Key Messages	<p>Disseminate information about modules developed in HIT2GAP (FDD and Forecasting).</p> <p>Get feedback about customer needs.</p>		
HIT2GAP connection	<p>Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs.</p> <p>Presentation of several functionalities of the platform.</p>		

Name	La Matinale du COBATY BORDEAUX métropole - "Bâtiments intelligents"	19
Action type	WS-I	
Location	Bordeaux (France)	Date 13/04/2017
Partners	NBK	
Link	http://www.smartbuildingsalliance.org/mc-events/la-matinala-du-cobaty-batiments-intelligents	
Description	Participation in smart city association event	
Audience type	I-SW, I-BMS, I-ESCO, PB	Reach 100
Key Messages	<p>Platforms for Energy Management for buildings and resilient neighbourhoods – HIT2GAP and DR-BOB</p> <p>How to address the energy performance gap, Interoperability, building versus district scale</p> <p>Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to actors involved in digital building, standardisation (Ready2Services), building and energy management,</p>	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs. Presentation of several functionalities of the platform.	

Name	Article in energy Efficiency dissemination portal "EnergieImpulse"	20
Action type	CONF, EU-EEB	
Location	Berlin, Germany	Date 03/05/2017
Partners	FISE	
Link	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1172913	
Description	Article in Berliner Energie Impulse e-magazine	
Audience type	CON, P-FM	Reach 250
Key Messages	<p>Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to general public in a specialized energy efficiency magazine in Germany</p> <p>Present the HIT2GAP innovative solution developed in the project</p>	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables; Presentation of the whole project: context, objectives and developed solutions.	

Name	Wrokshop at the Berliner Energietage	21
Action type	EXH, WS-I	
Location	Berlin, Germany	Date 03/05/2017
Partners	BRE - FISE	
Link	https://www.energietage.de/fileadmin/user_upload/2017/Aussteller/BET_2017_Ausstellerunterlagen.pdf	
Description	Organization of a workshop at the Exhibition Berliner Energietage. about energy efficiency in for businesses. "Gebäudeperformance im Betrieb optimieren. "	
Audience type	I-ESCO, P-EM	Reach 165

Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to general public in a specialized energy efficiency magazine in Germany
	Present the HIT2GAP innovative solution developed in the project
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables; Presentation of the whole project: context, objectives and developed solutions.

Name	Participation in the UCAMI 2016 conference	22
Action type	CONF	
Location	Gran Canaria (Spain)	Date 03/11/2016
Partners	TEK	
Link	http://mami.uclm.es/ucami-2016/	
Description	Presentation of: "Efficient Management of Data Models in Constrained Systems by Using Templates and Context Based Compression"	
Audience type	HEI, RI, PB-IT	Reach 50
Key Messages	Present the HIT2GAP innovative solution developed in the project to an audience of IT professionals and IT academics	
HIT2GAP connection	WP1 and WP2	

Name	Basque Energy Cluster	23
Action type	UPEV	
Location	Donostia - San Sebastian	Date 09/05/2017
Partners	GIR,TEK	
Link	http://www.clusterenergia.com/home	
Description	The Basque Energy Cluster is made up of the leading companies in the energy sector located in the Basque Country (energy operators, component and equipment manufacturers), agents of the Basque Science, Technology and Innovation Network and public administration bodies involved in the energy field. The Cluster is a non-profit organisation , which was set up at the end of 1996 within the framework of the Basque Government's policy to foster the competitiveness of the industrial sector. It is currently made up of over one hundred companies and entities active in the energy sector.	
Audience type	G-L / P-EM	Reach 20
Key Messages	To promote and disseminate HIT2GAP project, find synergies and put in contact our implementations.	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	San Sebastian city local authorities	24
Action type	UPEV	
Location	Donostia - San Sebastian	Date 30 May 2017

Partners	GIR		
Link	http://www.fomentosansebastian.eus/en/		
Description	Technological globe "Fomento de San Sebastián S.A" is a public municipal company dedicated to the promotion and the economic and social development of the city through innovation, the generation and transformation of knowledge, networking, and the promotion and management of projects, all in accordance with criteria of sustainability		
Audience type	G-L	Reach	5
Key Messages	To promote and disseminate HIT2GAP project, find synergies and share experiences		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	Vitoria city local authorities – Presentation of the Smartency project to the Coronacion district	25
Action type	SHF / H2020	
Location	Vitoria-Gasteiz	Date 26-27/05/2017
Partners	GIR	
Link	http://www.smartcityexpo.com/en/	
Description	The city of Vitoria organises a meeting with the neighbours of the Coronacion district due to the deployment of the European project: Smartency. There was a stand of Giroa-Veolia in order to give information. It is a good opportunity to provide information and receive inputs from the rest of the members of the consortium.	
Audience type	G-L / EU-H2020	Reach 200
Key Messages	To promote and disseminate HIT2GAP project.	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	Sustainable Places Conference 2017	26
Action type	CONF	
Location	Middlesbrough (UK)	Date 28-30/06/2017
Partners	R2M	
Link	http://www.sustainableplaces.eu/previous/sp2017/	
Description	Presentation "Highly innovative building control tools tackling the energy performance gap" Andrea Costa, R2M Solution.	
Audience type	EU-H2020, PP	Reach 110
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	Big Data for a Better Energy Performance	27
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Action type	CONF		
Location	Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour, Pau (France)	Date	30/06/2017
Partners	NBK		
Link	http://iutpa.univ-pau.fr/fr/actualites/colloque-big-data-performance-energetique.html		
Description	Participation in a colloquium		
Audience type	PP, HEI, PB-EN, PB-IT, PB-BS, I-ESCO	Reach	100
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP What are the mains challenges associated with data science applied to building energy management?		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and Deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	Performer workshop event	28
Action type	EU-EEB	
Location	Paris	Date 13/07/2017
Partners	BFM-TP	
Link	http://performerproject.eu/newsroom/	
Description	Presentation of HIT2GAP in a joint event workshop with sister project PERFORMER.	
Audience type	PP - RI	Reach 50
Key Messages	Discussion with similar project focused on the energy performance gap reduction	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	Building Simulation 2017	29
Action type	CONF	
Location	San Francisco, USA	Date 07-09/08/2017
Partners	BRE, UOS	
Link	http://www.buildingsimulation2017.org/ www.ibpsa.org	
Description	Building Simulation 2017 will bring together practitioners and researchers from around the world to share information about the state of the art in simulation tools and applications and to discuss new developments. The conference will feature updates and insights regarding new research to improve simulation capabilities for advanced low-energy building systems, case studies from successful projects that demonstrate the key role that simulation plays, and ongoing efforts to enable compliance and building rating software to support radiant and other energy efficient systems.	

	Two papers were presented: “A 'big data' approach to the application of building performance simulation to improve the operational performance of large estates” and “CALIBRO: an R Package for the Automatic Calibration of Building Energy Simulation Models”.		
Audience type	PP, HEI, PB-EN, PB-IT, PB-BS	Reach	800
Key Messages	To promote HIT2GAP at the largest Building Simulation research and practice event in the world.		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	CISBAT 2017	30
Action type	CONF	
Location	Lausanne, Switzerland	Date 06-08/09/2017
Partners	NBK	
Link	http://cisbat.epfl.ch/index.html	
Description	Partners presented the paper “ <u>HIT2GAP: Towards a better building energy management</u> ”. The conference focused on energy efficiency and the use of solar energy in the built environment, CISBAT offers a dynamic international platform for scientific exchange in fields ranging from nanostructured materials for renewable energy applications to urban energy systems. CISBAT is organised for the 14 th time by the Solar Energy and Building Physics Lab (LESO-PB) of the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Lausanne (EPFL).	
Audience type	PP, HEI, PB-EN, PB-IT, PB-BS	Reach 240
Key Messages	To promote and disseminate HIT2GAP project, find synergies and share experiences	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	AEE WEE 2017	31
Action type	CONF	
Location	Atlanta (GA). USA	Date 28-29/09/2017
Partners	ENE	
Link	http://www.energycongress.com/ https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1005828	
Description	The World Energy Engineering Congress (WEEC) is the largest energy conference and technology expo held in the U.S. specifically for business, industrial and institutional energy users. It brings together the top experts in all areas of the field to help you set a clear, optimum path to energy efficiency, facility optimization and sustainability.	
Audience type	PP, HEI, PB-EN, PB-IT, PB-BS	Reach 300

Key Messages	To promote HIT2GAP at one of the largest Energy conference in the world.
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.

Name	Stakeholders Workshop in BRE	32
Action type	WS-IN	
Location	Gavenscraig. Motherwell (UK)	Date 16/08/2016
Partners	BRE	
Link	N/A	
Description	A stakeholder meeting was held at the BRE Innovation Park in Ravenscraig on 16 August 2016. Presentations were given by BRE and UoS, followed by discussions where attendees were asked to consider a number of questions relevant to HIT2GAP.	
Audience type	HEI, REI, I-GC	Reach 11
Key Messages	Post Occupancy Evaluation Building occupancy loads	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	Stakeholders Workshop in BRE	33
Action type	WS-IN	
Location	East Kilbride (UK)	Date 19/04/2017
Partners	BRE	
Link	N/A	
Description	A stakeholder meeting took place in April 2017 in East Kilbride. The meeting included discussions of some of the HIT2GAP modules that are being developed.	
Audience type	HEI, REI, I-GC	Reach 5
Key Messages	Modules presentation	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	CoopIS 2017	34
Action type	CONF	
Location	Rhodes (Greece)	Date 25/10/2017
Partners	NBK	
Link	https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/events/coopis-2017_en	
Description	Cooperative Information Systems (CIS) facilitate the cooperation between individuals, organizations, smart devices, and systems of systems, which provide flexible, scalable and intelligent services to	

	enterprises, public institutions and user communities. As a result, people and smart devices can interact, share information and work together across physical barriers typically exploiting cloud-based environments. The Cooperative Information Systems (CIS) paradigm integrates the research results from many related computing areas, such as: distributed systems, coordination technologies, process management, knowledge management, collective decision making, and systems integration technologies, while the core are the organizational and business models that help selecting, shaping and managing at the technological solutions.		
Audience type	PP, HEI, PB-EN, PB-IT, PB-BS	Reach	150
Key Messages	Dissemination to scientific community Presentation describing the following theme: Using Colored Petri Nets for Verifying RESTful Service Composition.		
HIT2GAP connection	WP 4 – Integration and HIT2GAP API		

Name	Energy Performance Gap Article in NOBATEK/INEF4 newsletter	35
Action type	ARTICLE	
Location	France	Date 12/09/2017
Partners	NBK	
Link	N/A	
Description	Article in the NOBATEK-INEF4 periodic newsletter	
Audience type	PUB, G-L, G-N, RI, I-GC, P-FM	Reach 250
Key Messages	Energy Performance Gap	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	Smartcity Expo World Congress	36
Action type	CONF	
Location	Barcelona	Date 14-16/11/2017
Partners	EUR, UDG	
Link	http://www.smartcityexpo.com/en/	
Description	Smart City Expo World Congress aims to attract more than 118 companies not only from Spain but also from different parts of the world and the products will come from sectors like Energy and Sustainability, Mobility and Transport, Environment and Recycling, ICT and Research, Urban Planning as well as Cities. The exhibits will also come from fields like mobility, town planning, environment, information and communication technologies, energy consumption, knowledge economy and governance.	
Audience type	All	Reach More than 500
Key Messages	To promote and disseminate HIT2GAP project, find synergies and share experience with other companies.	

HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.
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Name	International Research and Innovation Centre in Intelligent Digital Systems (IRIXYS) 2017	37
Action type	WS-AC	
Location	Hendaye (France)	Date 30/11/2017
Partners	NBK	
Link	http://irixys.uni-passau.de/workshop19/	
Description	Workshops organised by International research and innovation Centre in Intelligent Digital Systems	
Audience type	RI	Reach 50
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to scientific community Using Colored Petri Nets for Verifying RESTful Service Composition	
HIT2GAP connection	WP4	

Name	Participation at the 5 th LDCAC 2017 conference	38
Action type	CONF	
Location	Dijon (France)	Date 13-15/11/2017
Partners	NBK – LIU – EGE - EUR	
Link	http://linkedbuildingdata.net/ldac2017/	
Description	Presentation of the communication titled “OntoH2G: A semantic model to represent building infrastructure and occupant interactions”	
Audience type	RI - HEI	Reach 50
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to scientific community	
HIT2GAP connection	WP4 – Occupant Behaviour Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	Presentation at the CSTB Doctoriales	39
Action type	Pitch Event	
Location	CSTB, Paris (France)	Date 25/01/2018
Partners	NBK	
Link	http://www.cstb.fr/en/	
Description	Pitching event	
Audience type	RI	Reach 90
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to scientific community Gathering of feedback	

HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.
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Name	Web HOTAL round table	40
Action type	WS-IN	
Location	Athens (Greece)	Date 11/02/2018
Partners	API	
Link	N/A	
Description	Invited speaker to the round table “Web Hotal”	
Audience type	I – GC, I-RE	Reach 60
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to Industry groups Connected with User Behaviour modules	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	Participation at HORECA exhibition	41
Action type	WS-IN	
Location	Athens (Greece)	Date 08-11/02/2018
Partners	API	
Link	https://horecaexpo.gr/en/visitors/exhibition-floor-plan/	
Description	Presentation titled “Modelling, monitoring and controlling user behaviour as regards energy use”.	
Audience type	I – GC, I-RE	Reach 200
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to Industry groups Connected with User Behaviour modules	
HIT2GAP connection	WP1 (T1.5), WP2 (T2.5), WP3 (T3.5)	

Name	Poster presentation at the RYAN INSTITUTE Research Day	42
Action type	WS-AC	
Location	Galway	Date 03/05/2018
Partners	NUIG	
Link	http://www.nuigalway.ie/ryaninstitute/	
Description	Poster presentation and networking event at the Ryan Institute.	
Audience type	RI - RFA	Reach 50
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to the academic community in Ireland Present the HIT2GAP innovative solution developed in the project	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables;	

Name	Participation in the 3 rd . CESCIT 2018 conference			43
Action type	CONF			
Location	Faro (Portugal)	Date	6-8/06/2018	
Partners	UDG			
Link	N/A			
Description	Presentation of the paper titled “Fault detection and diagnosis web service module for energy monitoring in buildings”			
Audience type	RI – HEA – PB-IT	Reach	50	
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to the academic community			
	Present the HIT2GAP innovative solution developed in the project			
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables;			

Name	Article in NOBATEK Annual Activity report			44
Action type	ARTICLE			
Location	France	Date	06/2018	
Partners	NBK			
Link	https://www.nobatek.inef4.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/NOBATEK_INEF4_FOCUS-2018_HD.pdf			
Description	Annual activity report of NOBATEK-The HIT2GAP project among other European projects is described in the section dedicated to open innovation and finalised research of the document.			
Audience type	ALL	Reach	250	
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to the industry community			
	Present the HIT2GAP innovative solution developed in the project			
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables;			

Name	Presentation at the EU-China Symposiums on Sustainable Energy, Energy Efficiency and Phase Change Energy Storage Technologies – Hull University			45
Action type	WS-AC			
Location	University of Hull (UK)	Date	30/07/2018	
Partners	R2M			
Link	https://www.eu-china-rseest-hull2018.com/			
Description	Presentation titled “Why behaviour? Modelling, Monitoring and Controlling User Behaviour as regards Energy Use”.			
Audience type	RI - RFA	Reach	120	
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to Industry groups			
	Connected with User Behaviour modules			

HIT2GAP connection	WP1 (T1.5), WP2 (T2.5), WP3 (T3.5)
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Name	Participation at the SIMAUD conference	46
Action type	CONF	
Location	Delft (Netherlands)	Date 4-7/06/2018
Partners	EGE – BES – TP-BFM	
Link	http://www.simaud.org/2018	
Description	Presentation of the paper “To participate or not to participate? Selecting the Right Participant Profile for Thermal and Visual Comfort Studies”	
Audience type	RI - HEI	Reach 300
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach to Industry groups Connected with User Behaviour modules	
HIT2GAP connection	WP1 (T1.5), WP2 (T2.5), WP3 (T3.5)	

Name	Sustainable Places Conference 2018	47
Action type	WS-AC	
Location	Aix-Les-Bains (FRANCE)	Date 27 th -29 th June 2018
Partners	R2M	
Link	http://www.sustainableplaces.eu/previous/sp2018/	
Description	Collaborative workshop covering 3 EU H2020 sister projects addressing 1. Data Management, 2. Citizen (occupant) engagement: active or passive, 3. Replicability & Business Modelling, 4. Upscaling Energy Management from Buildings to Block of Buildings, 5. Building Performance Optimisation & Gap Reduction	
Audience type	RI - RFA	Reach 110
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	The Internet of Things Week	48
Action type	CONF and WS-IN	
Location	Bilbao (Spain)	Date 04/06/2018
Partners	BRE – TEK – GIR	
Link	https://iotweek.org/iot-week-bilbao/	
Description	Participation in the IOT week conference	
Audience type	I-BMS, I-WSCO, I-SW	Reach 50

Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.

Name	Jornadas de la Eficiencia Energetica “Hacia la clasificacion”	49
Action type	CONF and WS-IN	
Location	Bilbao (Spain)	Date 26/10/2017
Partners	GIR - TEK	
Link	http://www.clusterenergia.com/ekitaldiak/anese-y-eve-organizan-jornada-eficiencia-energetica-ruta-ee-eses-hacia-clasificacion-2	
Description	Participation in a conference with the talk “Giroa-Veolia como ESE: Casos de Ahorro mediante renovación de instalaciones” by José Alonso-Urquijo, Director Comercial.	
Audience type	I-BMS, I-WSCO, I-SW, G-L, G-N, I-FM	Reach 30
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	Berdeago Energy – Feria Vasca de la Eficiencia Energetica	50
Action type	EXH	
Location	Durango (Spain)	Date 19/01/2018
Partners	GIR	
Link	https://www.berdeago.com/feria/	
Description	Participation in an energy fair representing VEOLIA-GIROA and HIT2GAP as a success case study	
Audience type	I-GC, I-RE, I-ESCO	Reach 150
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	Veolia “Open Door Day”	51
Action type	PEV	
Location	Zamudio (Spain)	Date 15/05/2017
Partners	GIR	
Link	N/A	
Description	Presentation at VEOLIA open door day	
Audience type	I-GC, I-RE, I-ESCO	Reach 40

Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.

Name	Project presentation to VEOLIA clients (IMQ Group)	52
Action type	WS-IN	
Location	Zamudio (Spain)	Date 17/01/2018
Partners	GIR	
Link	N/A	
Description	Presentation of HIT2GAP to Certification and Testing company IMQ Group with an interest in ISO 50001 certification	
Audience type	I-BMS, I-ESCO, P-FM	Reach 10
Key Messages	Highlight potential of HIT2GAP platform for certification and energy analysis at the core business of IMQ group activities.	
HIT2GAP connection	WP6 – New generation of energy services.	

Name	Creative Construction Conference 2018	53
Action type	CONF	
Location	Ljubljana (Slovenia)	Date 30/06/2018
Partners	EGE - BES	
Link	https://www.diamond-congress.hu/creative-construction-conference-2018/	
Description	Presentation of the paper “Application of heart rate variability for thermal comfort in office buildings in real-life conditions”	
Audience type	HEI, RI, P-EM	Reach 200
Key Messages	Importance of thermal comfort and occupant behaviour in energy management in buildings Integration of Thermal Comfort within innovative services platform HIT2GAP	
HIT2GAP connection	WP3	

Name	Digitaler Wandel - Chancen für die Betriebsführung beim Betrieb von Anlagen der Technischen Gebäude Ausrüstung (TGA)	54
Action type	WS-IN	
Location	Frankfurt (Germany)	Date 28/06/2018
Partners	BRE - FISE	
Link	N/A	
Description	Participation in an Industry workshop	
Audience type	I-ENG	Reach 20

Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	5 th International Project and Construction Management Conference (IPCMC 2018), Cyprus, 16-18 November 2018		55
Action type	WS-IN		
Location	Cyprus	Date	16-18/11/2018
Partners	EGE - LIU		
Link	http://pcmc2018.ciu.edu.tr/		
Description	Participation in a conference with the paper titled “ Do Gender and Age Group Affect Thermal Sensation? A Field Study in an Office Building ”		
Audience type	I-ENG, PB-CM, HEI	Reach	20
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	Building Resilience – a Glimpse into The Future of Energy Modelling & Beyond		56
Action type	WS-AC		
Location	Blantyre (UK)	Date	08/06/2018
Partners	BRE – UOS		
Link	N/A		
Description	Presentation of HIT2GAP in an academic workshop oriented to industry		
Audience type	PB, P-EM, RI	Reach	30
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects.		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	Keynote address, IBPSA ENGLAND conference		57
Action type	CONF		
Location	Cambridge (UK)	Date	12/09/2018
Partners	BRE-UoS		
Link	https://www.bso2018.event.cam.ac.uk/programme		
Description	Prof. Joe Clarke presented HIT2GAP platform in his keynote address opening of the BSO conference with the talk titled “The future of building performance simulation”.		

Audience type	HEI, REI	Reach	130
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	8 th ECTP conference 2018-Innovative Built Environment		58
Action type	CONF, EU-EEB		
Location	Brussels, Belgium	Date	13/11/2018
Partners	NBK		
Link	https://fr.xing-events.com/ECTPConference2018.html		
Description	<p>The 8th ECTP open Conference was dedicated to present and discuss current and anticipated innovation in the built environment field. Plenary sessions with high-level speakers from academia, industry and the European Commission introduced the global scheme and visions from various stakeholders. Meanwhile, thematic parallel sessions addressed diverse specific issues under the five current challenges of the ECTP. A hall for booths and posters exhibited examples of innovation from recent and ongoing European projects.</p>		

Audience type	PP, PB, G-EN, RFA, FI, HEI, EU-H2020	Reach	100
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach, find synergies and share experience with other projects. Present the HIT2GAP innovative solution developed in the project		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project: context, objectives and developed solutions.		

Name	uSIM – IBPSA Scotland Conference – Closing Keynote Address		59
Action type	CONF		
Location	Glasgow (UK)	Date	30/11/2018
Partners	BRE – UOS		
Link	http://www.esru.strath.ac.uk/Documents/Proceedings/uSIM18/usim_index.htm		
Description	Closing keynote address by Prof. Joe Clarke		
Audience type	HEI, REI	Reach	35
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	XII Jornadas de Innovacion en Servicios Generales Hospitalarios		60
Action type	EXH		
Location	Santander (Spain)	Date	06/06/2018
Partners	GIR		

Link	https://forohospitalario.org/santander2018/		
Description	Stand in Exhibition targeting the Hospital Management and Health Services sector in Spain.		
Audience type	G-L, G-N, G-EN, I-ENG, I-RE	Reach	50
Key Messages	Application of innovative web-based platforms for the management of Hospitals.		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	Digitalización en el sector de los equipos y sistemas termicos para el sector terciario	61
Action type	WS-IN	
Location	Zamudio (Spain)	Date 27/09/2019
Partners	GIR	
Link	N/A	
Description	Presentation in a dedicated talk to industry sector regarding digitalization of HVAC equipment.	
Audience type	I-ENG	Reach 20
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	EESAP 9 / CICA 2	62
Action type	CONF – EXH	
Location	Bilbao (Spain)	Date 10-12/09/2018
Partners	GIR	
Link	https://www.uik.eus/en/9o-congreso-europeo-sobre-eficiencia-energetica-y-sostenibilidad-en-arquitectura-y-urbanismo-eesap-9	
Description	<p>The 9th edition of the European Congress on Energy Efficiency and Sustainability in Architecture and Urbanism (EESAP 9) and the 2nd International Congress on Advanced Construction (CICA 2) approached the issue of Smart Communities, which is based on the need to incorporate human scale and its nearby area as an essential variable for cities intelligent management, as a consequence of current society's aim to achieve higher levels of life quality.</p> <p>Mr Gorka Naveran presented HIT2GAP in a talk titled "Digitalización de las infraestructuras y su aproximación hacia instalaciones 4.0"</p>	

Audience type	PB-AR, PB-EN, PB-CM, PB-BS, P-FM, P-EM	Reach	100
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	BIM World 2019	63
Action type	CONF – EXH	
Location	Paris (France)	Date 02/04/2019
Partners	NBK	
Link	https://bim-w.com	
Description	Participation as exhibitor in the biggest fair related to digitalization in construction BIM World.	

Audience type	G-L, G-N, I-BMS, I-SW, PB-IT, PB-AR, PB-ENG, I-GC	Reach	100
Key Messages	BEMServer has been officially launched in a dedicated booth at the BIM World 2019 fair. Several contacts have been taken during the event and were followed by commercial actions.		
HIT2GAP connection	WP6 and exploitation activities WP7 and dissemination activities		

Name	FUTUREBUILD 2019	64
Action type	WS-IN	
Location	London (UK)	Date 07/03/2019
Partners	BRE-UoS	
Link	N/A	
Description	<p>Futurebuild is the evolution of ecobuild and fulfilment of the bold vision for the future that we first announced following the acquisition of the event at the end of 2016. Futurebuild 2019 brings together opinion-shapers, decision-makers and product innovators under a common purpose to explore the latest technologies and approaches, and debate the biggest issues facing the built environment – now and in the future – both in the UK and overseas.</p> <p>BEMServer was presented in a dedicated talk by Lori McElroy (BRE) and Daniel Costola (UoS)</p>	

Audience type	G-L, G-N, I-BMS, I-SW, PB-IT, PB-AR, PB-ENG, I-GC	Reach	15
Key Messages	Presentation of BEMServer.		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	BEMServer Article in NOBATEK/INEF4 newsletter	65
Action type	ARTICLE	
Location	France	Date 18/04/2019
Partners	NBK	
Link	N/A	
Description	Article in the NOBATEK-INEF4 periodic newsletter	
Audience type	PUB, G-L, G-N, RI, I-GC, P-FM	Reach 250
Key Messages	Presentation of BEMServer.	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	IEEE ICWS 2019	66
Action type	CONF	
Location	Milan (Italy)	Date 08/07/2019
Partners	NBK – LIU	
Link	https://conferences.computer.org/icws/2019/	
Description	Lara Kallab presented “Automatic K-Resources Discovery for Hybrid Web Connected environments” in relation with a functionality of the BEMServer solution for composing automatically webservices attached to the platform.	

Audience type	PB-IT, I-BMS, I-SW	Reach	50
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables and especially to WP4; Presentation of a specific functionality of BEMServer.		

Name	Brokerage Event – ECTP Conference		67
Action type	H2020		
Location	Brussels (Belgium)	Date	12/06/2019
Partners	NBK		
Link	N/A		
Description	Participation in a brokerage event previous to the ECTP Conference. Nobatek did a 5 minutes presentation of BEMServer with the view on potential further collaborations.		
Audience type	EU-H2020	Reach	80
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	Article in DPArquitectura		68
Action type	ARTICLE		
Location	Spain	Date	05/07/2019
Partners	NBK -GIR – EUR - UDG		

Link	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3385093		
Description	Article in a web magazine		
Audience type	PB-AR, PB-EN, P-FM	Reach	100
Key Messages	Generic dissemination of HIT2GAP to the Architecture and Engineering professional in Spain.		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	SMARTHOME Exhibition	69
Action type	EXH	
Location	Athens (Greece)	Date 11/05/2019
Partners	API	
Link	http://indelex-smarthomexpo.eu/en/visitor/exhibitor-list	
Description	Participation with a stand in the SmarHOME exhibition.	
Audience type	I-BMS, I-SW, P-FM, PUB	Reach 80
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP modules in a Trade Fair	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	Presentation of HIT2GAP – BEMSERVER to NANOGUNE	70
Action type	SHF	
Location	San Sebastian (Spain)	Date 13/06/2019
Partners	TEK – GIR – NBK – EUR – UDG	
Link	N/A	
Description	<p>Dissemination to local stakeholders and visit to NANOGUNE pilot site regarding innovative outcomes of the project.</p>	

Audience type	RI, PP, GL, HEI, PB-E	Reach	40
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	MAPIC 2018	71
Action type	EXH	
Location	Cannes (France)	Date 14/11/18
Partners	R2M	
Link	http://www.territoires-marketing.fr/salon-mapic-2018/	
Description	Participation in the Exhibition targeting Real Estate Developers and Facility Managers.	
Audience type	I-GC, I-RE, P-FM	Reach 50
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP outcomes	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	2019 European Conference on Computing in Construction	72
Action type	CONF	
Location	Chania (Greece)	Date 10/07/2019
Partners	NBK - CYR	
Link	https://youtu.be/zA2PUwGgB4I	
Description	<p>Rafael Constantinou presented a paper titled “BEMSERVER: AN OPEN SOURCE PLATFORM FOR BUILDING ENERGY PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT”</p> <p>Presentation Video:</p>	
Audience type	PB-IT, I-SW	Reach 50
Key Messages	General dissemination of HIT2GAP and BEMSERVER	

HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		
Name	4 th International Sustainable Buildings Symposium (ISBS2019)	73	
Action type	CONF		
Location	Dallas (US)	Date	18/06/2019
Partners	EGE		
Link	http://www.isbs2019.gazi.edu.tr/		
Description	Gulben Calis (EGE) presented a paper titled “Comparing the Accuracy of Energy Prediction Models Based on Hourly and Daily Mean Outdoor Temperature”		
Audience type	RFA, HEI, RI, PB-A, PB-C, PB-E	Reach	300
Key Messages	Use of modelling to predict energy consumption using HIT2GAP data acquisition platform		
HIT2GAP connection	WP2, WP3, WP4		

Name	MIPIM Cannes 2019	74	
Action type	EXH		
Location	Cannes (France)	Date	12/03/19
Partners	R2M		
Link	https://immo2.pro/agenda/salon-immobilier/mipim-cannes-2019/		
Description	Participation in the Exhibition targeting Real Estate Developers and Facility Managers.		
Audience type	I-GC, I-RE, P-FM	Reach	50

Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP outcomes
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.

Name	RE+BUILD – Piattaforma per L’innovazione delle costruzioni italiane. 2019	75
Action type	EXH	
Location	Milano (Italy)	Date 25/06/2019
Partners	R2M	
Link	http://www.rebuilditalia.it/it/programma-milano-2019/	
Description	Participation in a convention regarding Innovation in construction targeting Italian professional sectors. Alessandro Lodigliani presented HIT2GAP innovative solutions as invited panelist in a round table.	
Audience type	I-GC, I-RE, P-FM	Reach 50
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP outcomes	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	2 nd International Congress on Engineering and Architecture (ENAR)	76
Action type	CONF	
Location	Marmaris (Turkey)	Date 22/04/2019
Partners	EGE	
Link	https://www.enarcongress.com/	
Description	Gulben Calis presented a paper titled “BEMServer And Occupant Behaviour: A New Approach Towards Addressing The Energy Gap in Buildings”	
Audience type	RFA, HEI, RI, PB-A, PB-C, PB-E	Reach 250
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP outcomes Thermal comfort models and occupant behaviour modules integration in HIT2GAP pilot sites.	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	Creative Construction Conference – CCC2019	77
Action type	CONF	
Location	Budapest (Hungary)	Date 29/07/2019
Partners	EGE	
Link	https://2019.creative-construction-conference.com/detailed-program/	

Description	Participation in the conference with the paper titled “Do Thermal Comfort Standards Ensure Occupant Satisfaction? Learning From Occupants’ Thermal Complaints”		
Audience type	RFA, HEI, RI, PB-A, PB-C, PB-E	Reach	200
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP outcomes Thermal comfort models and occupant behaviour modules integration in HIT2GAP pilot sites.		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	Berdeago Energy 2019 – Feria Vasca de la Eficiencia Energetica	78
Action type	EXH	
Location	BILBAO (Spain)	Date 01/02/2019
Partners	GIR	
Link	https://www.berdeago.com/feria/	
Description	<p>Participation in an energy fair representing VEOLIA-GIROA and HIT2GAP as a success case study. Annual edition of the energy fair whose program is characterized by different activities and events, with the aim of raising awareness in society and show the latest developments in products and services in environment, sustainability and energy efficiency.</p>	
Audience type	I-GC, I-RE, I-ESCO	Reach 610
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	University Days - UPV	79
Action type	WS-A	
Location	Bilbao (Spain)	Date 13/02/2019
Partners	GIR	
Link	N/A	
Description	Talk aimed at University of the Basque Country (Universidad del Pais Vasco) students in order to explain the company and the different projects in R+D.	
Audience type	HEI	Reach 100
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP outcomes	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	Infoconstruccion Conferencias – Vitoria	80
Action type	CONF	
Location	Vitoria (Spain)	Date 28/02/2019
Partners	GIR	
Link	https://eventos.infoconstruccion.es/diadelarehabilitacionenvitoriagasteiz	
Description	<p>Giroa-Veolia attended to the Infoconstrucción conferences consisting in architecture and construction area that took place in Vitoria-Gasteiz (Spain) and are periodically developed in several locations in Spain. In these talks, Giroa-Veolia presented the different projects that are currently working with the aim of bringing the latest developments in the air conditioning sector to the general public and the specific sectors (construction, conditioning, energy ... etc).</p> <p>J.A Urquijo presented HIT2GAP in a talk titled: “Digitalización de las instalaciones y su aproximación hacia instalaciones 4.0 a través de proyectos de I+D”</p>	
Audience type	PB, PB-AR, PB-EN, P-EM.	Reach 150

Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP outcomes
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.

Name	Infoconstrucion – Jaca	81
Action type	CONF	
Location	Jaca (Spain)	Date 30/05/2019
Partners	GIR	
Link	https://eventos.infoconstruccion.es/jaca2019jornadaprofesionaldeconstruccion	
Description	Professionaly focused event in Jaca (Spain). HIT2GAP project was presented by Mr. Gorka Naveran in a talk titled “ <i>Digitalización de las instalaciones y su aproximación hacia instalaciones 4.0 a través de proyectos de I+D</i> ”	
Audience type	PB, PB-AR, PB-EN, P-EM.	Reach 100
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP and sharing achievements and progress with similar projects	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.	

Name	Infoconstruccion Conferencias – Gijon	82
Action type	CONF	
Location	Gijon (Spain)	Date 21/03/2019
Partners	GIR	
Link	https://eventos.infoconstruccion.es/gijoninnovacionenproductosysistemasparalaconstruccion	
Description	Giroa-Veolia attended to the Infoconstrucción conferences consisting in architecture and construction area that took place in Gijon (Spain) and are periodically developed in several locations in Spain. In these talks, Giroa-Veolia presented the different projects that are currently working with the aim of bringing the latest developments in the air conditioning sector to the general public and the specific sectors (construction, conditioning, energy ... etc).	

	<p>Mr. Gorka Naveran presented HIT2GAP in a talk titled “Digitalización de las instalaciones y su aproximación hacia instalaciones 4.0 a través de proyectos de I+D”.</p>			
Audience type	PB, PB-AR, PB-EN, P-EM.	Reach	100	
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP outcomes			
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.			

Name	Infoconstruccion Conferencias – San Sebastian		83
Action type	CONF		
Location	San Sebastian (Spain)	Date	07/05/2019
Partners	GIR		
Link	https://eventos.infoconstruccion.es/donostiasansebastianinnovacionenproductosysistemasparalaconstruccion		
Description	<p>Giroa-Veolia attended to the Infoconstrucción conferences consisting in architecture and construction area that took place in Donostia-San Sebastian (Spain) and are periodically developed in several locations in Spain. In these talks, Giroa-Veolia presented the different projects that are currently working with the aim of bringing the latest developments in the air conditioning sector to the general public and the specific sectors (construction, conditioning, energy ... etc).</p> <p>Mr. Gorka Naveran presented HIT2GAP in a talk titled “Digitalización de las instalaciones y su aproximación hacia instalaciones 4.0 a través de proyectos de I+D”.</p>		

Audience type	PB, PB-AR, PB-EN, P-EM.	Reach	200
Key Messages	Dissemination of HIT2GAP outcomes		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables; Presentation of the whole project.		

Name	Europe Greenbuild International Conference		84
Action type	CONF		
Location	Amsterdam, Netherland	Date	18/03/2019
Partners	R2M		
Link	https://www.usgbc.org/articles/greenbuild-europe-2019-be-held-amsterdam		
Description	A presentation about features of the project and the developed solutions was given during this international conference.		
Audience type	PP, PB, PB-EN, P-FM, P-EM, HEI, RI	Reach	100
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach. BEMServer features and opportunities, modules capabilities.		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables		

Name	MADE expo e Agorà: BEM: Building Energy Modeling - Il BIM applicato all'energia		85
Action type	WS-IN, WS-AC		
Location	Milan, Italy	Date	14/03/2016
Partners	R2M		
Link	https://www.madeexpo.it/en/eventi-convegni/buildsmart/Costruzioni/BIMlab-3.html https://www.exposave.com/		

Description	A presentation about features of the project and the developed solutions was given during this exposition about building systems and BMSs, at national level.		
Audience type	PB, I-BMS, P-FM	Reach	100
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach, solutions and outcomes.		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables		

Name	REHVA Workshop “Closing the quality gap: from design to real buildings”.	86
Action type	WS-IN, WS-PB, WS-AC, CPD	
Location	Venice, Italy	Date 21/02/2019
Partners	R2M	
Link	http://www.aicarr.org/Pages/Convegni/VENEZIA%202019/Rehva_Workshop.aspx	
Description	<p>The session dealt with the topic of the performance gap between the design phase and real operation life in buildings focusing on quality and added value approaches that cover the entire Building Life Cycle. Starting from the Green Building Council experience on quality and sustainability the session continued on both the experience of EU projects funding under the H2020 by the European Commission that are addressing this topic.</p> <p>Basing on the research activities and real application on field performed in some international research project ad HIT2GAP, Quantum BIM4REN and Built2Spec, available tools and procedures to reduce the gap were presented. HIT2GAP offers an on-line platform which can integrate several informatic modules covering a large variety of relevant solutions to close the performance gap, as faults diagnosis and detection, load forecasting, building performance simulation and related energy models calibration, uncertainty and sensitivity analysis, user behaviour analysis and others. Quantum project has developed specific software tools to check in easier and accurate way if building systems work according to the quantitative targets and functions defined in the planning phase, a software tool to offer comprehensive and fast comfort survey to building users, and an easy and cost-effective systems of components to monitor the performance of buildings and systems. In the workshop, these solutions have been presented also focusing on application in real buildings and construction sites. The session closed with real buildings case studies where integrated design and BIM have led to high-end buildings and improved the overall process and building performance.</p>	
Audience type	PP, PB, PB-EN, P-FM, P-EM, HEI, RI	Reach 86
Key Messages	<p>Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach.</p> <p>BEMServer features and opportunities, modules capabilities.</p>	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables	

Name	Ecohouse - Fiera di Verona - DIGITALIZZAZIONE ED AUTOMAZIONE PER L'EDILIZIA SOSTENIBILE	87
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Action type	WS-IN, WS-AC		
Location	Verona, Italy	Date	08/02/2019
Partners	R2M		
Link	http://www.gbcitalia.org/web/guest/-/ecohouse-digitalizzazione-ed-automazione-per-l-edilizia-sostenibile		
Description	A presentation about features of the project and the developed solutions was given during this exposition about sustainable buildings and systems.		
Audience type	PB, I-BMS, P-FM	Reach	60
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach, solutions and outcomes.		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables		

Name	SAVE exhibition and fair	88
Action type	WS-IN, WS-AC	
Location	Verona, Italy	Date 19/10/2016
Partners	R2M	
Link	https://www.exposave.com/	
Description	A presentation about features of the project and the developed solutions was given during this exposition about systems, automations, BMSs, at national level.	
Audience type	PB, I-BMS, P-FM	Reach 20
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach, solutions and first outcomes.	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables	

Name	Digital construction skills: enabling the energy transition in Europe's building stock	89
Action type	WS-IN, WS-AC, EU-EEB	
Location	Barcelona, Spain	Date 16/05/2019
Partners	R2M	
Link	https://www.buildup.eu/en/news/register-build-skills-workshop-construmat19	
Description	We were invited by the European Commission and we presented HIT2GAP. Attendees were 75. Slides are available online and the event was widely published both before and after.	
Audience type	PB, I-BMS, I-ESCO, RI, I-GC, I-RE, P-FM, EU-H2020	Reach 75
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach. BEMServer features and opportunities. BEMServer modules capabilities.	
HIT2GAP	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables	

connection	
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Name	IERC 8th Annual Conference, 2019			90
Action type	CONF			
Location	Cork, Ireland	Date	11/04/2019	
Partners	R2M			
Link	http://www.ierc.ie/news/2019-conference/			
Description	A presentation about features of the project and the developed solutions was given during this international conference.			
Audience type	PP, PB, PB-EN, P-FM, P-EM, HEI, RI	Reach	20	
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach.			
	BEMServer features and opportunities, modules capabilities.			
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables			

Name	Sustainable Places conference 2019			91
Action type	WS-IN, WS-AC, EU-EEB			
Location	Cagliari, Italy	Date	05-07/06/2019	
Partners	R2M-NUIG			
Link	https://www.sustainableplaces.eu/previous/sp2019/			
Description	Poster of the project was exposed at the conference.			
Audience type	PB, I-BMS, I-ESCO, RI, I-GC, I-RE, P-FM, EU-H2020	Reach	181	
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach.			
	BEMServer features and opportunities.			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BEMServer modules capabilities. 			
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables			

Name	Sustainable Places conference 2019			92
Action type	WS-IN, WS-AC, EU-EEB			
Location	Cagliari, Italy	Date	05-07/06/2019	
Partners	NUIG			
Link	https://www.sustainableplaces.eu/previous/sp2019/			
Description	Presented the paper "ModSCO. Online Reduced Order Models (ROM) to Address the Performance Gap"			
Audience type	PB, I-BMS, I-ESCO, RI, I-GC, I-RE, P-FM, EU-H2020	Reach	50	
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach.			

	BEMServer features and opportunities.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simulation modules of HIT2GAP
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables

Name	XII Facility & Property Management conference	93
Action type	CONF	
Location	Warsaw (Poland)	Date 28/08/2019
Partners	MOS	
Link	http://pirbinstytut.pl/index.php/facility-management	
Description	<p>Błażej Rudzki of HIT2GAP's partner Mostostal presented the BEMServer solution for intelligent buildings to an audience of about 60 people at the XII Facility & Property Management conference in Warsaw on 28 August 2019 where the audience included a mixture of property owners, facility managers, property managers, developers, energy managers and architects. Attendees were given an overview of the BEMServer data platform and an introduction to a range of modules that sit on the platform to enable facility managers, engineers and other stakeholders to reduce the energy gap in buildings between actual energy use and projected energy use. The presentation included a description of the pilot building in Wilanow, which has been used to trial the BEMServer energy-saving solution.</p> <p>The XII Facility & Property Management conference was organized to present the latest trends in the field of real estate in Poland and the speakers included various experts on new technologies. The presentations at the conference included a wide variety of topics, including Building management systems, Video monitoring and access control, Automation and security systems in buildings, Fixed assets management, Big Data, Mobile and cloud technologies, Enterprise performance management, Project management, Quality planning and management, Facilities and equipment maintenance systems, Outsourcing (economic, technical, infrastructure), Green building, Usable space planning and management, Financial control, Customer relationship management, Real estate management, and Contract management.</p>	
Audience type	PB-CON, PB-BS, P-FM, I-RE, I-GC	Reach 60
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach.	
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables	

Name	The Future of Energy Management - Outcomes from the EU project HIT2GAP and launch of BEMServer, the world's first open source energy management platform.	94
Action type	WS-IN, WS-PB, WS-AC, CPD	

Location	Galway, Ireland	Date	29/08/2019
Partners	R2M - NUIG		
Link	https://www.eventbrite.ie/e/the-future-of-energy-management-launch-of-bemserver-the-worlds-premier-open-source-building-energy-tickets-70077857759?utm_term=eventurl_text#		
Description	<p>Outcomes from the EU project HIT2GAP and launch of BEMServer, the world's first open source energy management platform - Galway, Ireland, 29 August 2019. On 29 August, Galway, Ireland was the venue for an information evening about BEMServer, the world's premier open source building energy management platform. The aim of this CPD event was to discuss the topic of Building Energy Management in detail using the results of the HIT2GAP project, an EU - H2020 project aimed at reducing the gap between expected energy consumption and the actual energy consumption at the operational phase. Unlike traditional Building Management Systems which tend to be closed and fully automated, the HIT2GAP project explored a flexible open source platform into which a range of BMS tools could be plugged in to suit the users' requirements. The evening's proceedings included presentations on case studies using the BEMServer platform, a panel discussion and a tour of the building. The event was broadcasted and the video recording will be available in the HIT2GAP website.</p>		
Audience type	PP, PB, PB-EN, P-FM, P-EM	Reach	29
Key Messages	<p>Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach.</p> <p>BEMServer features and opportunities, modules capabilities.</p> <p>Presentation of the main results from the HIT2GAP pilot site NUIG Alice Perry Building in Galway.</p>		
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables		

Name	CLIMA 2019 Congress			95
Action type	CONF			
Location	Bucarest (Romania)	Date	26-29/05/2019	
Partners	R2M			
Link	https://www.clima2019.org/			
Description	Presented the paper "Hit2Gap Project: Highly Innovative building control Tools Tackling the energy performance gap"			
Audience type	REI, HEI, PB-AR, PB-IT,	Reach	50	
Key Messages	Disseminate the HIT2GAP approach.			
	BEMServer features and opportunities.			
HIT2GAP connection	Connected to ALL HIT2GAP WPs and deliverables			

3 Scientific Diffusion Activities

Scientific diffusion activities target academic and scientific audiences. As H2020 project, HIT2GAP partners have the obligation to make sure peer-reviewed journal articles published are openly accessible and free of charge.

All project publications are available in a public repository in ZENODO (see link below). This includes also public project deliverables, press releases, posters, softwares and pilot datasets:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/hit2gap/>

Figure 8 - Zenodo HIT2GAP community link

3.1 Scientific Publication Strategy

HIT2GAP scientific publication strategy and guidelines has been outlined in Deliverable 7.2- Appendix 3: “Guidelines for preparation of conference/journal papers.

3.2 Publications – Peer Reviewed Journal Papers

Title	“Short-term load forecasting for non-residential buildings contrasting artificial occupancy attributes”
Authors	J. Massana, C. Pous, L. Burgas, J. Meléndez, J. Colomer
HIT2GAP partners	UDG
Journal Name	Energy and Buildings
Journal Impact	2.973 (2015)
Correspondence	joaquim.melendez@udg.edu
DOI	https://dugi-doc.udg.edu/handle/10256/10941
HIT2GAP relevance	WP1, Task 1.3
Abstract	<p>An accurate short-term load forecasting system allows an optimum daily operation of the power system and a suitable process of decision-making, such as with regard to control measures, resource planning or initial investment, to be achieved. In a previous work, the authors demonstrated that an SVR model to forecast the electric load in a non-residential building using only the temperature and occupancy of the building as attributes is the one that gives the best balance of accuracy and computational cost for the cases under study. Starting from this conclusion, a simple, low-computational requirements and economical hourly consumption prediction method, based on SVR model and only the calculated occupancy indicator as attribute, is proposed. The method, unlike the others, is able to perform hourly predictions months in advance using only the occupancy indicator.</p> <p>Due to the relevance of the occupancy indicator in the model, this paper provides a complete study of the methods and data sources employed in the creation of the artificial occupancy attributes. Several occupancy indicators are defined, from the simplest one, using general information, to the most complex one, based on very detailed information. Then, a load forecasting performance discrimination between the artificial occupancy attributes is realized demonstrating that using the most complex indicator increases the workload and complexity while not improving the load prediction significantly. A real case study, applying the forecasting method to several non-residential buildings in the University of Girona, serve as a demonstration.</p>

Title	Identifying services for short-term load forecasting using data driven models in a Smart City platform
Authors	Burgas Nadal, Llorenç; Meléndez i Frigola, Joaquim; Colomer Llinàs, Joan; Pous i Sabadí, Carles; Massana i Raurich, Joaquim
HIT2GAP partners	UDG
Journal Name	Sustainable Cities and Society
Journal Impact	1.044 (2015)
Correspondence	joaquim.massana@udg.edu
DOI	https://dugi-doc.udg.edu/handle/10256/13412
HIT2GAP relevance	WP1, Task 1.3
Abstract	The paper describes an ongoing work to embed several services in a Smart City architecture with the aim of achieving a sustainable city. In particular, the main goal is to identify services required in such framework to define the requirements and features of a reference architecture to support the data-driven methods for energy efficiency monitoring or load prediction. With this object in mind, a use case of short-term load forecasting in non-residential buildings in the University of Girona is provided, in order to practically explain the services embedded in the described general layers architecture. In the work, classic data-driven models for load forecasting in buildings are used as an example.

Title	Context- and Template-Based Compression for Efficient Management of Data Models in Resource-Constrained Systems
Authors	Berzosa Macho, Jorge; Gardeazabal Montón, Luis; Cortiñas Rodríguez, Roberto
HIT2GAP partners	TEK
Journal Name	Sensors
Journal Impact	2.475 (2017)
Correspondence	jorge.berzosa@tekniker.es
DOI	https://doi.org/10.3390/s17081755
HIT2GAP relevance	WP2
Abstract	The Cyber Physical Systems (CPS) paradigm is based on the deployment of interconnected heterogeneous devices and systems, so interoperability is at the heart of any CPS architecture design. In this sense, the adoption of standard and generic data formats for data representation and communication, e.g., XML or JSON, effectively addresses the interoperability problem among heterogeneous systems. Nevertheless, the verbosity of those standard data formats usually demands system resources that might suppose an overload for the resource-constrained devices that are typically deployed in CPS. In this work we present Context- and Template-based Compression (CTC), a data compression approach targeted to resource-constrained devices, which allows reducing the resources needed to transmit, store and process data models. Additionally, we provide a benchmark evaluation and comparison with current implementations of the Efficient XML Interchange (EXI) processor, which is promoted by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), and it is the most prominent XML compression mechanism nowadays. Interestingly, the results from the evaluation show

	that CTC outperforms EXI implementations in terms of memory usage and speed, keeping similar compression rates. As a conclusion, CTC is shown to be a good candidate for managing standard data model representation formats in CPS composed of resource-constrained devices
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Title	N-dimensional extension of unfold-PCA for granular systems monitoring
Authors	Llorenç Burgas, Joaquim Melendez, Joan Colomer, Joaquim Massana, Carles Pous
HIT2GAP partners	UDG
Journal Name	Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence
Journal Impact	2.819 (2017)
Correspondence	llorenc.burgas@udg.edu
DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2018.02.013
HIT2GAP relevance	WP3
Abstract	<p>This work is focused on the data-based modelling and monitoring of a family of modular systems that have multiple replicated structures with the same nominal variables and show temporal behaviour with certain periodicity. These characteristics are present in many systems in numerous fields such as the construction or energy sector or in industry. The challenge for these systems is to be able to exploit the redundancy in both time and the physical structure. In this paper the authors present a method for representing such granular systems using N-dimensional data arrays which are then transformed into the suitable 2-dimensional matrices required to perform statistical processing. Here, the focus is on pre-processing data using a non-unique folding–unfolding algorithm in a way that allows for different statistical models to be built in accordance with the monitoring requirements selected.</p> <p>Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is assumed as the underlying principle to carry out the monitoring. Thus, the method extends the Unfold Principal Component Analysis (Unfold-PCA or Multiway PCA), applied to 3D arrays, to deal with N-dimensional matrices. However, this method is general enough to be applied in other multivariate monitoring strategies. Two of examples in the area of energy efficiency illustrate the application of the method for modelling. Both examples illustrate how when a unique data-set folded and unfolded in different ways, it offers different modelling capabilities. Moreover, one of the examples is extended to exploit real data. In this case, real data collected over a two-year period from a multi-housing social-building located in down town Barcelona (Catalonia) has been used.</p>

3.3 Publications – Conference Papers

Title	Towards a Data Driven Platform for Energy Efficiency Monitoring: Two Use Cases
Authors	<i>Melendez, Joaquim; Colomer, Joan; Pous, Carles; Burgas, Llorenç; Massana, Joaquim</i>

HIT2GAP partners	UDG
Conference	11 th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations (AIAI 2015): Vol-1539
Correspondence	joaquim.melendez@udg.edu
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.400290
HIT2GAP relevance	WP1, Task 1.3
Abstract	The paper describes an ongoing work to define a framework to support monitoring procedures for distribution systems in smart cities. Specific use cases, involving data driven methods for energy monitoring, benchmarking and forecasting in urban scenarios are analysed. The objective is to identify services required in such framework to define the requirements of a reference architecture to support data-driven methods for energy efficiency monitoring and assessment. Use cases focus on multi-entity buildings monitoring and consumption forecasting.

Title	Recent Developments in City Scale Modelling, Monitoring and Performance Information Delivery
Authors	<i>Joe Clarke</i>
HIT2GAP partners	UOS
Conference	11 th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations (AIAI 2015): Vol-1539
Correspondence	joe@esru.strath.ac.uk
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.400289
HIT2GAP relevance	WP1, Task 1.3, Task 1.4
Abstract	This paper corresponds to a presentation delivered at the SmarTABCD'15 workshop on Smart Technologies and Applications in Buildings, Cities and Districts organised within the framework of the 11 th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations. It reports outcomes from recent research that established a means to deliver, rapidly and at low cost, energy-related apps corresponding to discrete issues such as inappropriate HVAC system regulation, occupant discomfort avoidance, energy use reporting, upgrade quality assurance and the like.

Title	A Methodology to Develop a User-Behaviour Tool to Optimize Building Users' Comfort and Energy Use
Authors	<i>Gulben Calis¹, Aitor Corchero Rodriguez², Türkan Göksal-Özbalta¹, Regina Enrich Sard², Aitor Arnaiz³, Ignacio Lazaro³, Nikos Sakkas⁴</i>
HIT2GAP partners	EGE, EUR, TEK, API
Conference	SBE 16 Istanbul
Correspondence	gulben.calis@ege.edu.tr
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.398828
HIT2GAP relevance	To promote HIT2GAP aligned with Task 7.3
Abstract	The total amount of energy spent in buildings is quite significant, reaching up to 40% of the world's total energy usage. Accordingly, the EU has set goals requiring zero CO ₂ emission in buildings by 2020 to respond to the increasing energy demand and started continuously supporting innovative research approaches for improving energy efficiency in buildings. However, innovative approaches cover the challenges in specific parts (specific facilities, building functionalities, etc.) of both new

	<p>buildings and renovation of existing buildings. Therefore, main challenge in current building facilities is scaling up of the building innovative approaches in combination with the building usage. So, it is crucial to influence the complex interaction between users and buildings. To reinforce the building configuration and adaption according to the occupants' behaviour, this paper presents a methodology to construct a building-user interaction. This methodology aims at developing data mining algorithms and semantic models with stream reasoning capabilities that allows occupants and facility managers to monitor and control the energy consumption, to detect the energy inefficiencies and to generate recommendations to reduce energy consumption whilst increasing occupant comfort. The proposed methodology is modular which could be integrated in the existing building management systems and that is promising to reduce energy use in existing buildings.</p>
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Title	Efficient Management of Data Models in Constrained Systems by Using Templates and Context Based Compression
Authors	<i>Jorge Berzosa, Luis Gardeazabal, and Roberto Cortiñas</i>
HIT2GAP partners	TEK
Conference	UCAmI 2016, Canary Islands (Spain)
Correspondence	jorge.berzosa@tekniker.es
DOI	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-48799-1_38
HIT2GAP relevance	To promote the MM-WSN HIT2GAP interoperability approach developed in T2.2
Abstract	<p>Data communication is at the heart of any distributed system. The adoption of generic data formats such as XML or JSON eases the exchange of information and interoperability among heterogeneous systems. However, the verbosity of those generic data formats usually requires system resources that might not be available in resource-constrained systems, e.g., embedded systems and those devices which are being integrated into the so-called IoT.</p> <p>In this work we present a method to reduce the cost of managing data models like XML or JSON by using templates and context-based compression. We also provide a brief evaluation and comparison as a benchmark with current implementations of W3C's Efficient XML Interchange (EXI) processor. Although the method described in this paper is still at its initial stage, it outperforms the EXI implementations in terms of memory usage and speed, while keeping similar compression rates. As a consequence, we believe that our approach fits better for constrained systems.</p>

Title	HIT2GAP: Towards a better building energy management
Authors	<i>Kallab, Lara; Chbeir, Richard; Bourreau, Pierre; Brassier, Pascale; Mrissa, Michael</i>
HIT2GAP partners	NBK, LIU
Conference	CISBAT 2017 International Conference. Future Buildings & Districts. Energy Efficiency from Nano to Urban Scale, CISBAT 2017 6-8 September 2017, Lausanne, Switzerland
Correspondence	lkallab@nobatek.com ; lara.kallab@univ-pau.fr
DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.07.399

HIT2GAP relevance	WP4 – Description of the HIT2GAP platform
Abstract	Recent studies show that the Energy Performance Gap (EPGap), defined as the difference between the estimated and actual energy consumption of a building, is significantly high. This is due to various factors encountered in the different phases of the building life cycle, i.e.: inaccuracy of the specifications used in the simulation tools during design phase, poor quality of the on-site practices conducted throughout the construction, inadequate verification of the equipment installed in the building during commissioning phase, and limited analysis of the data collected from the equipment during the operational phase. With the aim of reducing the EPGap, we present an energy management framework defined in the context of an EU-funded H2020 project, HIT2GAP. The proposed solution provides several services from collecting heterogeneous on-site data, to advanced data analysis and visualization tools designed for the different actors of a building (e.g., building/facility/energy manager, occupants, etc.), for building energy performance optimization. In this paper, we give an overview on the proposed framework architecture and detail its different functionalities, with a particular focus on the solution Core Platform, which is in charge of orchestrating the different components, storing and structuring the data, and providing pre-processing services.

Title	A 'big data' approach to the application of building performance simulation to improve the operational performance of large estates
Authors	<i>Clarke, Joe; Costola, Daniel; Cowie, Andrew; Hand, Jon; Kelly, Nick; Monari, Filippo</i>
HIT2GAP partners	UOS – BRE
Conference	Building simulation 2017. 15 th IBPSA Conference San Francisco, CA, USA, Aug. 7-9, 201
Correspondence	joe@esru.strath.ac.uk
DOI	https://doi.org/10.26868/25222708.2017.68
HIT2GAP relevance	WP3
Abstract	This paper derives from the 'HIT2GAP' project as funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 R&D programme (HIT2GAP 2015). The aim of this project is to reduce the gap between design intent and the operational performance of large building estates. To this end, a data exchange platform is being established that is able to collect and store data from disparate sources, and deliver subsets of these data to a range of applications (services) intended to support facilities management. The ultimate aim is to identify physical interventions that will alleviate operational problems and so reduce the performance gap. This paper addresses the role of building performance simulation (BPS) within the Hit2Gap project, specifically: the fetching of an input model, its automated calibration, and its use in scripted applications for HVAC system fault detection and diagnosis, upgrade options appraisal, indoor environment quality improvement, energy demand reduction, renewable energy systems integration and control system refinement. The paper summarises the HIT2GAP architecture, the procedure for the automatic calibration of BPS models, and the invocation of cloud-based performance assessments in response to observed problems.

Title	CALIBRO: an R Package for the Automatic Calibration of Building Energy Simulation Models
Authors	<i>Filippo Monari, Paul Strachan</i>
HIT2GAP partners	UOS-BRE
Conference	Building simulation 2017. 15 th IBPSA Conference San Francisco, CA, USA, Aug. 7-9, 201
Correspondence	Filippo.Monari@strath.ac.uk
DOI	https://doi.org/10.26868/25222708.2017.22
HIT2GAP relevance	WP3
Abstract	Bayesian probability theory offers a powerful framework for the calibration of building energy models (Bayesian calibration). The major issues impeding its routine adoption are its steep learning curve, and the complicated setting up of the required calculation. This paper introduces CALIBRO, an R package which has the objective of facilitating the undertaking of Bayesian calibration of building energy models. An overview of the techniques and procedures involved in CALIBRO is given, as well as demonstrations of its capability and reliability through two examples.

Title	Using Coloured Petri Nets for Verifying RESTful Service Composition
Authors	<i>Kallab, Lara ; Mrissa, Michael ; Chbeir, Richard ; Bourreau, Pierre</i>
HIT2GAP partners	LIU – NBK
Conference	On the Move to Meaningful Internet Systems. OTM 2017 Conferences. OTM 2017 (OTM 2017), Rhodes, Greece, 23-27 October 2017
Correspondence	Lara.kallab@univ-pau.fr
DOI	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-69462-7_32
HIT2GAP relevance	WP2 – WP4
Abstract	RESTful services are an attractive technology for designing and developing web-based applications, as they facilitate reuse, interoperability, and loosely coupled interaction with generic clients (typically web browsers). Building RESTful service composition has received much interest to satisfy complex user requirements. However, verifying the correctness of a composition remains a tedious task. In this paper, we present a formal approach based on Colored Petri Nets (CPNs) to verify RESTful service composition. First, we show how CPNs are utilized for modelling the behaviour of resources and their composition. Then, we present how this formal model can be used to verify relevant composition behaviour properties. Our solution is illustrated with a scenario built upon an energy management web framework developed within the HIT2GAP H2020 European project (Highly Innovative building control Tools Tackling the energy performance GAP http://www.hit2gap.eu).

Title	OntoH2G: A semantic model to represent building infrastructure and occupant interactions
Authors	<i>Richard Chbeir, Aitor Corchero, Yudith Cardinale; Pierre Bourreau, Khouloud Salameh, Nathalie Charbel, Lara Kallab, Chinnapong Angsuchotmetee, and Gulben Calis</i>
HIT2GAP partners	LIU – NBK – EUT – EGE

Conference	LDAC2017 – 5 th Linked Data in Architecture and Construction Workshop (13 – 15 Nov. 2017) http://linkedbuildingdata.net/ldac2017/
Correspondence	rchbeir@acm.org
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1193292
HIT2GAP relevance	WP4
Abstract	In order to reduce the energy gap originated by the difference between existing tools estimations and real energy consumption, HIT2GAP European H2020 project aims at advancing on building control tools by providing a newer decision-making technology. Technically, HIT2GAP offers a platform inspired by previous reference architectures (e.g., Haystack) and complements them through a knowledge-based model, called OntoH2G, to store building information under a common vocabulary and consequently to enable fine-grained vision of the building with its equipment and occupants. OntoH2G allows to query building data so to extract required information and interesting events (through a set of services). OntoH2G advances over existing models on two main aspects: (i) being compliant with well-known ontologies in different domains in order to cover all energy building concepts, and (ii) its ability to represent user/occupant behaviour, preferences, and interactions.

Title	To participate or not to participate? Selecting the Right Participant Profile for Thermal and Visual Comfort Studies
Authors	<i>Calis, Gulben; Kuru, Merve; Mouawad, Jessica</i>
HIT2GAP partners	EGE – BES – TP-BFM
Conference	SimAUD 2018 Symposium on Simulation for Architecture and Urban Design 4-7/06/2018
Correspondence	Gulben.calis@ege.edu.tr
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1406978
HIT2GAP relevance	WP1 (T1.5) – WP2 (T2.5) – WP3 (T3.5)
Abstract	Energy consumption reduction in buildings poses great challenges to modern societies in which maintaining thermal and visual comfort is occupants' primary desire in indoor environments. In order to determine satisfaction levels of occupants, surveys are widely used to obtain feedback with respect to thermal and visual perceptions. However, low participation to the surveys might cause misleading results, and, thus, result in defining wrong strategies to maintain occupant comfort in buildings. Therefore, factors that affect participation to the surveys have to be analysed so that the surveys can be distributed to the most responsive profile. This study aims at investigating the relationship between factors related to participant profile (gender, age group, energy awareness level and the number of energy activities attended) and survey participation ratio. A survey was conducted in an office building in France between December 19, 2016 and September 25, 2017. A total of 93 occupants participated in the study. The relationship between participation ratio and the occupant related factors were analysed via Kruskal-Wallis tests. The results show that the energy awareness level has a statistically significant effect on the survey participation ratio whereas gender and age group have not a significant effect on the survey participation ratio. Therefore, this result is a proof that the energy

	awareness levels of occupants have to be increased in order to reach higher participation ratios.
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Title	Fault detection and diagnosis web service module for energy monitoring in buildings
Authors	<i>J. Meléndez, L. Burgas, F.I. Gamero, J. Colomer, S. Herraiz</i>
HIT2GAP partners	UDG
Conference	3 rd IFAC Conference on Embedded Systems, Computational Intelligence and Telematics in Control – CESC – 6-8/06/2018
Correspondence	sergio.herraiz@udg.edu
DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2018.06.229
HIT2GAP relevance	WP3
Abstract	This work presents the development of a web service module for monitoring energy consumption data recorded in buildings. This software is based on the application of Principal Component Analysis (FDD-PCA module) and it is one of the results of the H2020 project HIT2GAP. The aim of these Web Services is to implement a fault detection and diagnosis software module to detect abnormal energy consumptions or misbehaviours. The result can be integrated into an architecture to facilitate the access and management of data coming from the different energy subsystems (and other sources of data as meteorological information) involved in the operation of a building.

Title	Closing the Gap for Optimal Building Energy Performance through an ISO 50001 Energy Management System
Authors	<i>Mike Brogan: alfiio Galata</i>
HIT2GAP partners	ENE
Conference	World Energy Engineering Congress 2017 (WEEC 2017) , Atlanta (GA) - USA, 17-19 Oct 2017
Correspondence	mike.brogan@enerit.com
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1005828
HIT2GAP relevance	WP1 – WP5
Abstract	In the energy performance of buildings, there is always a gap between the designed energy consumption and actual operation that is difficult to mitigate or close. This GAP can be positive or negative; in practice, it is usually negative because actual performance turns out much worse than expected. The cause can be erroneous simulations, poor construction methods or operational practices with devices as well as users not operating as expected. Thus, interventions along any of three fundamental life-cycle directions: design, build, operation can reduce this GAP. Usually the bigger gaps arise from numerous operational issues that deteriorate the performance, well beyond expectations. Recent studies in the field of energy efficient buildings have shown that ICT solutions, user behaviour and energy policy, considered as a whole process within an organization, can have a significant impact on building energy use. As a result, significant energy savings opportunities can be achieved by influencing the involved stakeholders, to adopt systematic energy management practices. The 4 year EU H2020 HIT2GAP project has identified that the gap can be reduced by optimizing the following: simulation-calibration, disaggregation, forecasting, building performance

	assessment, energy management, user behaviour, multiple set-point control, fault detection and diagnosis. The HIT2GAP project will deliver an open solution with analytic tools and modular services for commercial buildings. The paper describes the Energy Management (EnMS) module, within the HIT2GAP platform, which allows to build a systematic approach to Energy Management based on ISO 50001 standard. The ISO 50001 standard specifies detailed requirements for establishing the EnMS and improving the overall building energy performance. The HIT2GAP platform is currently being piloted in 3 building complexes in 3 countries in Europe and preliminary results will be presented.
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Title	Application of heart rate variability for thermal comfort in office buildings in real-life conditions
Authors	<i>Fernandez, Sergio; Lazaro, Ignacio; Calis, Gulben</i>
HIT2GAP partners	EGE - TEK
Conference	Creative Construction Conference 2018 (CCC 2018), Ljubljana, Slovenia, 30 June - 3 July 2018
Correspondence	santiago.fernandez@tekniker.es
DOI	https://doi.org/10.3311/CCC2018-104
HIT2GAP relevance	WP2
Abstract	In the context of building efficiency, occupants' preferences can be considered as a source of information complementary to those in traditional building management systems (BMS). The general availability of wearable devices in recent years has increased interest in this ecosystem of technologies, as well as in their practical applications and those that can potentially derive from them. This study aims at investigating the applicability of wearable heart rate sensors for evaluating aspects of mood associated to stress/comfort, and in particular in relation to thermal comfort. A procedure for data gathering and analysis is proposed and tested in an office building in real-life conditions. First results show that no clear pattern of comfort vs. discomfort can be observed in data during testing. In addition, some of the challenges of applicability of the technique in real-life conditions are discussed in the study.

Title	Do Gender and Age Group Affect Thermal Sensation? A Field Study in an Office Building
Authors	<i>Kuru, M; Calis, Gulben; Mouawad, Jessica</i>
HIT2GAP partners	EGE - BES
Conference	5th International Project and Construction Management Conference (IPCMC 2018), Cyprus, 16-18 November 2018
Correspondence	j.mouawad@bouygues-es.com
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3382300
HIT2GAP relevance	WP2
Abstract	In the context of building efficiency, occupants' preferences can be considered as a source of information complementary to those in traditional building management systems (BMS). The general availability of wearable devices in recent years has increased interest in this ecosystem of technologies, as well as in their practical applications and those that can potentially derive from them. This study aims at

	investigating the applicability of wearable heart rate sensors for evaluating aspects of mood associated to stress/comfort, and in particular in relation to thermal comfort. A procedure for data gathering and analysis is proposed and tested in an office building in real-life conditions. First results show that no clear pattern of comfort vs. discomfort can be observed in data during testing. In addition, some of the challenges of applicability of the technique in real-life conditions are discussed in the study.
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Title	BEMSERVER: AN OPEN SOURCE PLATFORM FOR BUILDING ENERGY PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT
Authors	<i>Bourreau, Pierre; Chbeir, Richard; Cardinale, Yudith; Corchero, Aitor; Salameh, Khoulood; Lafréchoux, Jérôme; Frédérique, David; Calis, Gulben; Kallab, Lara; Constantinou, Rafael</i>
HIT2GAP partners	NBTK – LIU – ASC – EGE - CYR
Conference	2019 European Conference on Computing in Construction, Chania, Crete, Greece, 10-12 July 2019
Correspondence	p.bourreau@nobatek.inef4.com
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3382308
HIT2GAP relevance	All WPs
Abstract	In the era of new technologies and with the growing need for reliable ecological energy supplies, researchers eyes are diverted towards reducing the energy consumption of buildings which becomes a major concern that requires a variety of actors being involved (e.g., building owners, energy/facility managers, occupants, data scientist), who have different expertise and need to use different tools. This paper introduces BEMServer, an open source Building Energy Management system solution built to ease the integration of data analytic and visualization services into building and energy domain applications. It handles heterogeneous data in a transparent way by providing a clear and unambiguous semantic representation of the modelled resources. To do so, BEMServer integrates the OntoH2G formal ontology at its core. The architecture of BEMServer, the design and use of OntoH2G in the solution, as well as the suitability of BEMServer as a middleware in the H2020 project Hit2Gap are described

Title	ModSCO. Online Reduced Order Models (ROM) to Address the Performance Gap
Authors	<i>Piccinini, Alessandro; Blanes, Luis M.; Seri, Federico; D'Angelo Letizia; Keane, Marcus M.</i>
HIT2GAP partners	GAL
Conference	Sustainable Places 2019 (SP 2019), Sardinia, Italy, 5–7 June 2019. (SP 2019), Sardinia, Italy, 5–7 June 2019.
Correspondence	Alessandro.piccinini@nuigalway.ie
DOI	https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings2019020018
HIT2GAP relevance	WP3
Abstract	This communication presents ModSCO, a web application that supports systematic energy performance evaluation using Reduced Order Models (ROM). These models are particularly useful in scenario with missing, incomplete or uncertain building information. The paper describes the

	theory behind ROM grey-box modelling and presents case studies that support the smart operation of energy systems by generating Energy Conservation Opportunities (ESCOs) for instance, to help ISO 50001 implementation. The ROM demonstrated to provide accurate results with a reduced effort. The acceptable calibration tolerance provided by the ASHRAE Guideline 14 is been used to demonstrate the ROM's accuracy. Additionally, the ModSCO architecture and user interface is also described.
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Title	BEMServer And Occupant Behaviour: A New Approach Towards Addressing The Energy Gap in Buildings
Authors	<i>Calis, Gulben; Kuru, Merve</i>
HIT2GAP partners	EGE
Conference	2nd International Congress on Engineering and Architecture (ENAR) Marmaris / Turkey, 22 - 24 April 2019 (ENAR), Marmaris / Turkey, 22 - 24 April 2019
Correspondence	Gulben.calis@ege.edu.tr
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3378769
HIT2GAP relevance	WP2
Abstract	The actual energy consumption of buildings in Europe often exceeds design energy predictions by a significant margin. This gap between actual energy performance and design energy performance can arise from construction errors, commissioning errors and/or the way buildings are actually used. Moreover, occupant behaviour is now widely recognized as a major contributing factor to this gap. HIT2GAP is a Horizon 2020 EU-funded project that seeks to reduce the gap between predicted and actual energy consumption of buildings. To do this, HIT2GAP develops an energy management platform (BEMServer) which could eliminate this gap in existing buildings, by providing a data platform, energy predictions and benchmarks as well as modules that address the concerns of facility and energy managers. This study presents the BEMServer and the semantic driven behaviour module that is developed within the HIT2GAP project. The architecture of the BEMServer as well as the behaviour module's functionalities, the outputs and the use cases are provided.

Title	Do Thermal Comfort Standards Ensure Occupant Satisfaction? Learning From Occupants' Thermal Complaints
Authors	<i>Kocaman, Ezgi; Kuru, Merve; Calis, Gulben</i>
HIT2GAP partners	EGE
Conference	2nd International Congress on Engineering and Architecture (ENAR) Marmaris / Turkey, 22 - 24 April 2019 (ENAR), Marmaris / Turkey, 22 - 24 April 2019
Correspondence	Gulben.calis@ege.edu.tr
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3378813
HIT2GAP relevance	WP2
Abstract	Today, buildings are operated according to the standards (i.e. thermal), however; the recommended values in the standards might not necessarily address occupants' needs, and, thus, occupant complaints might arise. This study aims at assessing the performance of the

	<p>predicted mean vote (PMV) model to detect occupant thermal dissatisfaction. The case study was conducted in a commercial building located in Paris, France between January 2017 and May 2018. Indoor environmental conditions were monitored via sensors and an online tool was used to collect occupant thermal complaints. A total of 53 thermal complaints were analyzed and the corresponding measurements were checked against the reference values suggested by the ISO 7730 Thermal Comfort Standard. The results show that all of the operative temperature measurements both in the heating and cooling seasons were within the thresholds suggested by the standards. In addition, the PMV method suggested that only 4% of the occupants were dissatisfied with the indoor environment. However; the actual dissatisfaction ratio of occupants was 100% under these indoor environmental conditions. The findings of this study show that predefined comfort ranges, and, thus thermal comfort standards are not able to predict occupant thermal dissatisfaction.</p>
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Title	HIT2GAP Project: Highly Innovative building control Tools Tackling the energy performance gap
Authors	<i>Costa, Andrea; Pietrobon, Marco; Messervey, Thomas</i>
HIT2GAP partners	R2M
Conference	CLIMA 2019, Bucarest, Romania, 26-29 May 2019
Correspondence	Andrea.costa@r2msolution.com
DOI	https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/201911105023
HIT2GAP relevance	WP6
Abstract	<p>Measurement campaigns have shown major discrepancies in buildings energy performance between planned energy demand and real energy consumption, while nowadays most of the newly constructed offices buildings are equipped with BMS systems, integrating a more or less extended measurement layer providing large amounts of data. The HIT2GAP project has developed a new generation of building monitoring and control tools based on advanced data treatment techniques allowing new approaches to assess building energy performance data, getting a better understanding of building's behaviour and hence a better performance. From a strong research layer on data, HIT2GAP solution builds on existing measurement and control tools that are embedded into a new software platform for performance optimization. The HIT2GAP solution is applied as a novel intelligent layer offering new capability of the existing BMS systems and offering the management stakeholders opportunities for services with a novel added value. Applying the solutions to groups of buildings also allows to test energy demand vs. local production management modules. This solution is being tested in various pilot sites across Europe. HIT2GAP work has been carried out with a permanent concern about market exploitation of the solutions developed within the project. This paper will present the project solution in detail and showcase the achievement so far in the real case demo sites.</p>

Title	Automatic K-Resources Discovery for Hybrid Web Connected Environments
Authors	<i>Kallab, Lara; Chbeir, Richard; Mrissa, Michael</i>
HIT2GAP partners	LIU – NBK
Conference	International Conference on Web Services (ICWS) 2019 (ICWS 2019), Milano, Italy, 8-13 July 2019
Correspondence	lkallab@nobatek.inef4.com
DOI	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02265473/document
HIT2GAP relevance	WP4
Abstract	<p>Recently, RESTful services, designed as resources, have seen their popularity rising and have shown their potential in composing reliable Web-scale environments (Web applications, Web platforms, Web of Things (WoT), etc.). However, discovering the necessary resources for a composition is becoming more challenging. This is due to 1) the growing number of published Web-based resources, and 2) the highly dynamic nature of the WoT environment, in which smart devices, connected to the Web platform, are exposed as resources. In this paper, we propose an automatic resource discovery, applicable in hybrid Web-based environments providing static linked resources always available on the Web, and connecting dynamic resources that can be connected to and removed from the Web at different time periods. The solution presents an indexing schema that makes resource discovery process fast, especially in large-scale environments. Experiments were conducted in different environment setups to test the effective performance of our approach.</p>

Title	DENSITY-BASED CLUSTERING ALGORITHM FOR FAULT DETECTION AND IDENTIFICATION IN HVAC SYSTEMS
Authors	<i>Benndorf, Gesa Angelika; Rehault, Nicolas</i>
HIT2GAP partners	FISE
Conference	BauSIM 2016, Dresden, Germany, 14-16 September 2016
Correspondence	nicolas.rehault@ise.fraunhofer.de
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3385118
HIT2GAP relevance	WP2 – WP3
Abstract	<p>The operation of building services like heating, ventilation and air conditioning systems (HVAC systems) is often vitiated by faults and sub optimal states. Such malfunctioning can be overcome by introducing a monitoring system with automated fault detection and diagnosis based on measurement data. Here, we propose a method for the automatic detection and identification of faults in HVAC systems, which is based on a clustering algorithm. We illustrate the proposed method using simulation data from a simple model, where faults have been implemented artificially, and show that the approach performs well with respect to fault detection and that it provides additional valuable information to enable fault diagnostics.</p>

3.4 Publications – PhD Thesis

Title	Data-Driven models for building energy efficiency monitoring PhD Thesis
Authors	<i>J. Massana</i>
HIT2GAP partners	UDG
Correspondence	joaquim.massana@udg.edu
DOI	https://www.tdx.cat/handle/10803/482148
HIT2GAP relevance	WP3
Abstract	<p>Nowadays, energy is absolutely necessary all over the world. Taking into account the advantages that it presents in transport and the needs of homes and industry, energy is transformed into electricity. Bearing in mind the expansion of electricity, initiatives like Horizon 2020, pursue the objective of a more sustainable future: reducing the emissions of carbon and electricity consumption and increasing the use of renewable energies. As an answer to the shortcomings of the traditional electrical network, such as large distances to the point of consumption, low levels of flexibility, low sustainability, low quality of energy, the difficulties of storing electricity, etc., Smart Grids (SG), a natural evolution of the classical network, has appeared. One of the main components that will allow the SG to improve the traditional grid is the Energy Management System (EMS). The EMS is necessary to carry out the management of the power network system, and one of the main needs of the EMS is a prediction system: that is, to know in advance the electricity consumption. Besides, the utilities will also require predictions to manage the generation, maintenance and their investments. Therefore, it is necessary to dispose of the systems of prediction of the electrical consumption that, based on the available data, forecast the consumption of the next hours, days or months, in the most accurate way possible. It is in this field where the present research is placed since, due to the proliferation of sensor networks and more powerful computers, more precise prediction systems have been developed. Having said that, a complete study has been realized in the first work, taking into account the need to know, in depth, the state of the art, in relation to the load forecasting topic. On the basis of acquired knowledge, the installation of sensor networks, the collection of consumption data and modelling, using Autoregressive (AR) models, were performed in the second work. Once this model was defined, in the third work, another step was made, collecting new data, such as building occupancy, meteorology and indoor ambience, testing several paradigmatic models, such as Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Support Vector Regression (SVR), and establishing which exogenous data improves the prediction accuracy of the models. Reaching this point, and having corroborated that the use of occupancy data improves the prediction, there was the necessity of generating techniques and methodologies, in order to have the occupancy data in advance. Therefore, several attributes of artificial occupancy were designed, in order to perform long-term hourly consumption predictions, in the fourth work.</p>

3.5 Scientific Dissemination Summary

Date	Title	Journal	Conference	Link
17/09/2015	Towards a Data Driven Platform for Energy Efficiency Monitoring: Two Use Cases		AIAI 2015	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.400290
17/09/2015	Recent Developments in City Scale Modelling, Monitoring and Performance Information Delivery		AIAI 2015	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.400289
16/09/2016	DENSITY-BASED CLUSTERING ALGORITHM FOR FAULT DETECTION AND IDENTIFICATION IN HVAC SYSTEMS		BAUSIM 2016	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3385118
15/10/2016	Short-term load forecasting for non-residential buildings contrasting artificial occupancy attributes	Energy and Buildings		https://dugi-doc.udg.edu/handle/10256/10941
15/10/2016	A Methodology to Develop a User-Behaviour Tool to Optimize Building Users' Comfort and Energy Use		SBE 16	https://zenodo.org/record/398828
02/12/2016	Efficient Management of Data Models in Constrained Systems by Using Templates and Context Based Compression	Lecture Notes in Computer Science	UCAml 2016	https://zenodo.org/record/1173060
31/01/2017	Identifying services for short-term load forecasting using data driven models in a Smart City platform	Sustainable Cities and Society		https://dugi-doc.udg.edu/handle/10256/13412
07/06/2017	To Participate or not to Participate? Selecting the Right Participant Profile for Thermal and Visual Comfort Studies		SIMAUD 2018	https://zenodo.org/record/1406978
01/08/2017	Context- and Template-Based Compression for Efficient Management of Data Models in Resource-Constrained Systems	Sensors		http://europepmc.org/articles/PMC5579536
09/08/2017	A 'big data' approach to the application of building performance simulation to improve the operational performance of large estates		BS 2017	https://zenodo.org/record/1173080
09/08/2017	CALIBRO: an R Package for the Automatic Calibration of Building Energy Simulation Models		BS 2017	https://zenodo.org/record/1173078

30/09/2017	HIT2GAP: Towards a better building energy management	Energy Procedia	CISBAT 2017	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.07.399
19/10/2017	Closing the Gap for Optimal Building Energy Performance through an ISO 50001 Energy Management System		WEEC 2017	https://zenodo.org/record/1005828
15/11/2017	OntoH2G: A semantic model to represent building infrastructure and occupant interactions		LDAC 2017	https://zenodo.org/record/1193292
27/02/2018	Using Colored Petri Nets for Verifying RESTful Service Composition		OTM 2017	https://zenodo.org/record/1193256
30/05/2018	N-dimensional extension of unfold-PCA for granular systems monitoring	Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2018.02.013
08/06/2018	Fault detection and diagnosis web service module for energy monitoring in buildings	IFAC-PapersOnLine	CESCIT 2018	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2018.06.229
03/07/2018	Application of heart rate variability for thermal comfort in office buildings in real-life conditions		CCC 2018	https://zenodo.org/record/3382290
19/11/2018	Do Gender and Age Group Affect Thermal Sensation? A Field Study in an Office Building		IPCMC 2018	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3382300
31/05/2019	BEMServer And Occupant Behaviour: A New Approach Towards Addressing The Energy Gap in Buildings		ENAR 2019	https://zenodo.org/record/3378769
02/07/2019	Do Thermal Comfort Standards Ensure Occupant Satisfaction? Learning From Occupants' Thermal Complaints		CCC2019	https://zenodo.org/record/3378813
12/07/2019	BEMSERVER: AN OPEN SOURCE PLATFORM FOR BUILDING ENERGY PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT		EC3 2019	https://zenodo.org/record/3382308
20/07/2019	Comparing the Accuracy of Energy Prediction Models Based on Hourly and Daily Mean Outdoor Temperature		ISBS 2019	https://zenodo.org/record/3403217
25/07/2019	ModSCO. Online Reduced Order Models (ROM) to Address the Performance Gap	MDPI Proceedings	Sustainable Places 2019	https://www.mdpi.com/2504-3900/20/1/18
13/08/2019	Hit2Gap Project: Highly Innovative building control Tools Tackling the energy performance gap	E3S Web of Conferences	CLIMA 2019	https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/201911105023

29/08/2019	Automatic K-Resources Discovery for Hybrid Web Connected Environments	ICWS 2019	https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02265473/document
PhD Thesis			
02/02/2018	Data-Driven models for building energy efficiency monitoring	Universitat de Girona	http://hdl.handle.net/10803/482148
09/09/2019	A Context- and Template-Based Data Compression Approach to Improve Resource-Constrained IoT Systems Interoperability	Universidad del Pais Vasco	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3403230
Work in progress			
	Integrated Unfold-PCA monitoring application for smart buildings: An AHU application example (Burgas et. al.)		Under 1 st . revision – Applied Energy - ELSEVIER
	Multivariate statistical modelling and monitoring of smart buildings (Loorenc Burgas)		Submitted for VIVA – UdG

4 Social Media Communications

4.1 HIT2GAP Web Page Communication activity report

HIT2GAP Website is accessible from www.hit2gap.eu. Figure 9 below shows the landing page.

Figure 9: The HIT2GAP new webpage layout (www.hit2gap.eu)

The site has been completely redesigned and includes the following sections:

- Home: Landing page with tweeter feed;
- About the project: Now includes the modules description;
- Pilot projects: Description of the buildings tested in Hit2GAP, including two new

videos;

- Get Involved: Links to contact points in each country;
- Documents: New section with links to downloadable documents regarding journal publications, promotional communications such as newsletters and updates, and public deliverables;
- News & Events: on-going feed of events, news related to HIT2GAP;
- Contact Us: general email contact form;
- Search: search engine (internal reach headers search);

Figure 10 below, provided by Google, shows a summary statistical view of the HIT2GAP webpage from. HIT2GAP webpage was launched in September 2015. The site has received **8,626 page views** from the Aug 2016 to Sept 2017 period. The same period the page registered approximately 3000 sessions and for the period August 2017 to Feb 2017 there were 1200 sessions (6 months period). The graphs below show that approximately the page registers **consistently 200 visits per month**.

Figure 10: August 2016 – September 2017 webpage statistics

Figure 11: August 2017 – February 2018 webpage statistics

Figure 12: March 2018 – Sep 2018 webpage statistics

An interesting fact about the reach of the web is the returning visitor rate. The statistics for the months April and June 2018 show a 20.1% of returning visitors. Most of the visitors (79.9 %) are new visitors. Returning visitors tend to stay on the site for longer periods.

The top countries of origin of the website were France and Spain with 19.24 % and 14.14% of the visitors respectively. Regarding visits outside the EU space, the page registered traffic from Lebanon, Ukraine and the United States.

For the final 12 months of the project, from 1 September 2018 to 31 August 2019, the website received about 500 page views per month. Typically, this consisted of around 180 sessions per month with around 2.6 pages per session.

Table 2 - Table of statistics for the period 1 September 2018 to 31 August 2019

Website users	1471
Sessions per user	1.50
Sessions	2213
Pages per session	2.59
Average session duration	2 minutes, 25 seconds
Bounce rate	54.99%

Of the website sessions during the period 1 September 2018 to 31 August 2019, the main countries of origin (for website sessions) were France (18.0% of sessions), Spain (12.7%), United Kingdom (12.3%), United States (10.4%), Italy (7.1%), Ireland (6.1%), Germany (3.9%), Poland (3.5%), Turkey (3.3%) and India (1.7%).

4.2 HIT2GAP Newsletter and additional communications

4.2.1 HIT2GAP – Newsletter ONE

HIT2GAP first newsletter was distributed manually by email in February 2016.

The newsletter is available here: <http://en.calameo.com/read/0046186047b57624d9b9f>. No statistical data is available.

4.2.2 HIT2GAP – Newsletter TWO – Statistics

HIT2GAP second newsletter was issued in November 2016.

Newsletter Two Statistics are based on three different mailing lists which were used to disseminate the Newsletter, user *MailChimp.com*. Below we show the summary statistics for these three mail lists. Currently there are no statistics tracking available showing direct downloads of the Newsletter from the HIT2GAP webpage.

The newsletter is available here:

<https://us13.campaign-archive.com/?u=a5479cdf18e28b805c476dafc&id=968680a5ca>.

HIT2GAP Project Team Mailing List – sent to 256 recipients via MailChimp	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject: HIT2GAP – Newsletter Two – November 2016 • Delivered: Mon, Nov 07, 2016 3:40 pm 	
Open and Clicks	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open rate 29.8% • List average 29.0% • Industry average (Construction) 20.5% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Click rate 4.5% • List average 5.9% • Industry average (Construction) 2.2%
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of people who opened – 73 • No. of people who clicked – 11 • Bounced – 11 • Unsubscribed – 5 • Successful deliveries – 245 (95.7%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total opens – 162 (includes multiple by same person) • Forwarded – 0 • Clicks per unique opens – 15.1% • Total clicks – 15
Top links clicked	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 – http://www.hit2gap.eu/blog • 4 – General meeting held in Paris • 2 – http://www.hit2gap.eu 	

C4R – sent to 354 recipients via MailChimp	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subject: HIT2GAP – Newsletter Two Delivered: Mon, Nov 07, 2016 3:45pm 	
Open and Clicks	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open rate <u>28.9%</u> List average 24.8% Industry average (Construction) 20.5% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Click rate 0.3% List average 2.6% Industry average (Construction) 2.2%
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No. of people who opened – 98 No. of people who clicked – 1 Bounced – 15 Unsubscribed – 7 Successful deliveries – 339 (95.8%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total opens – 179 (includes multiple by same person) Forwarded – 0 Clicks per unique opens – 1.0% Total clicks – 1
Top links clicked	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 – National Stakeholder Forum meeting 	

Enerit – sent to 499 recipients via MailChimp																					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subject: Closing the Gap in Building Energy Performance – HIT2GAP an EU H2020 Project Delivered: Apr 01, 2016 04:00 pm 																					
Open and Clicks																					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open rate 25.1% List average 22.1% Industry average (Software and Web App) 17.7% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Click rate 6.0% List average 3.5% Industry average (Software and Web App) 2.0% 																				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No. of people who opened – 104 No. of people who clicked – 25 Bounced – 84 Unsubscribed – 3 Successful deliveries – 415 (83.2%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total opens – 277 (includes multiple by same person) Forwarded – 0 Clicks per unique opens – 24.0% Total clicks – 46 																				
Top links clicked																					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6 – http://www.hit2gap.eu/blog/first-hit2gap-project-newsletter 20 – download pdf 																					
<p><i>Top locations by opens</i></p> <table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>	France	1	7.7%																		
	Ireland	3	23.1%																		
	Italy	3	23.1%																		
	United Kingdom	2	15.4%																		
	USA	2	15.4%																		
	France	1	7.7%																		

4.2.3 HIT2GAP – Newsletter THREE – Statistics

HIT2GAP third newsletter was issued in May 2017.

Newsletter Three Statistics are based on three different mailing lists which were used to disseminate the Newsletter, user *MailChimp.com*. Below we show the summary statistics for the six email lists considered. Currently there are no statistics tracking available showing direct downloads of the Newsletter from the HIT2GAP webpage.

The newsletter is available here:

<https://mailchi.mp/90f5977c2e07/hit2gap-newsletter-volume-1-may>.

HIT2GAP Project Team Mailing List – sent to 246 recipients via MailChimp																
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject: HIT2GAP Newsletter Three – May 2017 • Delivered: Fri, May 26, 2017 12:27 pm 																
Open and Clicks																
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open rate 32.5% • List average 29.0% • Industry average (Construction) 20.5% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Click rate 3.4% • List average 5.9% • Industry average (Construction) 2.2% 															
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of people who opened – 77 • No. of people who clicked – 8 • Bounced – 9 • Unsubscribed – 0 • Successful deliveries – 237 (96.3%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total opens – 159 (includes multiple by same person) Forwarded – 0 Clicks per unique opens – 10.4% Total clicks – 10 															
Top links clicked																
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7 – http://www.hit2gap.eu/about-the-project/update-on-work-package • 2 – http://www.hit2gap.eu • 1– Interview with Alfio Galata From Enerit 																
<p><i>Top locations by opens</i></p> <table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td> Turkey	11	7.1%														
USA	46	29.9%														
France	31	20.1%														
Spain	18	11.7%														
Cyprus	16	10.4%														
Turkey	11	7.1%														

4.2.4 HIT2GAP – Newsletter FOUR – Statistics

HIT2GAP fourth newsletter was issued in November 2017.

The newsletter is available here:

<https://us13.campaign-archive.com/?u=a5479cdf18e28b805c476dafc&id=7be5d11ee7>.

Newsletter FOUR Statistics are based on three different mailing lists which were used to disseminate the Newsletter, user *MailChimp.com*. Below we show the summary statistics for the six email lists considered. Currently there are no statistics tracking available showing direct downloads of the Newsletter from the HIT2GAP webpage.

HIT2GAP Project Team Mailing List – sent to 335 recipients via MailChimp																			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject: HIT2GAP Newsletter 4- Nov 2017 • Delivered: Wed, Nov 01, 2017 3:23 pm 																			
Open and Clicks																			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open rate 17.6 % • List average 24.8 % • Industry average (Construction) 20.5% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Click rate 1.3 % • List average 2.6 % • Industry average (Construction) 2.2% 																		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of people who opened – 55 • No. of people who clicked – 4 • Bounced – 23 • Unsubscribed – 5 • Successful deliveries – 312 (93.1%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total opens – 93 (includes multiple by same person) Forwarded – 0 Clicks per unique opens – 7.3% Total clicks – 5 																		
Top links clicked																			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 – http://www.hit2gap.eu/about-the-project/wp2 • 1 – http://www.hit2gap.eu/blog • 1– http://www.hit2gap.eu 																			
Top locations by opens																			
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Country</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>																			
Country	Count	Percentage																	
United Kingdom	77	85.6%																	
Canada	2	2.2%																	
Italy	2	2.2%																	
China	2	2.2%																	
France	1	1.1%																	

4.2.5 HIT2GAP – Newsletter FIVE – Statistics

HIT2GAP fifth newsletter was issued in June 2018;

The newsletter is available here:

<https://mailchi.mp/56d019175698/hit2gap-newsletter-1517877?e=ea4e7d6699>.

Newsletter FIVE Statistics are based on three different mailing lists which were used to disseminate the Newsletter, user *MailChimp.com*. Below we show the summary statistics for the six email lists considered. Currently there are no statistics tracking available showing direct downloads of the Newsletter from the HIT2GAP webpage.

HIT2GAP Project Team Mailing List – sent to 246 recipients via MailChimp																					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject: HIT2GAP Newsletter 5- June 2018 • Delivered: Fri, Jun 15, 2018 2:15 pm 																					
Open and Clicks																					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open rate 23.6 % • List average 29.0 % • Industry average (Construction) 20.5% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Click rate 3.0 % • List average 5.9 % • Industry average (Construction) 2.2% 																				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of people who opened – 55 • No. of people who clicked – 7 • Bounced – 13 • Unsubscribed – 3 • Successful deliveries – 233 (94.7%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total opens – 120 (includes multiple by same person) Forwarded – 0 Clicks per unique opens – 12.7% Total clicks – 11 																				
Top links clicked																					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 – www.hit2gap.eu/blog/an-interview-with-karen-molony-development-manager-at-cylon-controls-and-partner-of-hit2gap • 3 – http://www.hit2gap.eu/about-the-project/hit2gap-modules • 2 – You tube subscriber 																					
<p><i>Top locations by opens</i></p> <table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>	Ireland	11	9.6%																		
	France	24	21.1%																		
	USA	17	14.9%																		
	Turkey	13	11.4%																		
	Greece	13	11.4%																		
	Ireland	11	9.6%																		

4.2.6 HIT2GAP – Newsletter SIX – Statistics

HIT2GAP sixth newsletter was issued in August 2019; The newsletter is available here: <https://mailchi.mp/0e3353942eb2/hit2gap-newsletter-1849925> . For the first mailshot, the number of successful deliveries was 220 (i.e. 93.2%). The open rate was 14.5%, [the list average was 29.0% and the industry average (construction) was 20.5%]. The number of people who opened was 32, the number of people who clicked was 2, the number which bounced was 16 and the number which unsubscribed was 3. The total number of opens was 49. The number forwarded was 0. The click rate was 0.9%. [The list average was 5.9%, the industry average (construction) was 2.2%.] The proportion of clicks per unique opens was 6.3%. The total clicks was 2.

HIT2GAP Project Team Mailing List – sent to 236 recipients via MailChimp	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject: HIT2GAP Newsletter 6- August 2018 • Delivered: 28 August 2019, 2:31pm 	
Open and Clicks	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open rate 27.9 % • List average 28.2 % • Industry average (Construction) 20.5% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Click rate 3.2 % • List average 5.3 % • Industry average (Construction) 2.2 %
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No. of people who opened – 61 • No. of people who clicked – 7 • Bounced – 17 • Unsubscribed – 3 • Successful deliveries – 219 (93%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total opens – 215 (includes multiple by same person) Forwarded – 0 Clicks per unique opens – 11.5% Total clicks – 8700
Top links (in newsletter) clicked	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • http://www.hit2gap.eu - 9 • https://youtu.be/2haMALv8WwU - 8 • http://www.hit2gap.eu/blog - 8 • https://lnkd.in/gmHuTst - 6 • https://hit2gap.eu/about-the-project/wp5 - 5 	
(source: Mailchimp)	

NEWSLETTER 6

Sent 8/28/19 2:31PM

Opens by location

Country	Opens	Percent
USA	30	25.6%
Spain	13	11.1%
Italy	13	11.1%
France	12	10.3%
Germany	10	8.5%
Cyprus	7	6.0%
United Kingdom	7	6.0%
Turkey	6	5.1%
Poland	4	3.4%
Denmark	4	3.4%

4.3 Flipboard HIT2GAP activity report

Flipboard analytics are a useful instrument to monitor which communications impacted more among the readers, thus helping to elaborate a more concise and targeted communication style.

Analytics dashboards provide four metrics regarding the HIT2GAP Magazine statistics:

- Articles by day: Number of published articles (flipped) in the HIT2GAP magazine;
- Viewers by day: Number of readers who have seen items posted in the HIT2GAP magazine;
- Page flips by day: Number of views of per article per day in the HIT2GAP magazine;
- Followers: Number of people who follow the HIT2GAP magazine or are following the magazine authors.

Figure 13: Cover of HIT2GAP FLIPBOARD Magazine

HIT2GAP flipboard web version is available here:

<https://flipboard.com/@r2msolution/hit2gap-aeonq1icy>

Till date, the FLIPBOARD activity has grown steadily. The final figures are summarized below and in Figure 14 in the next page.

- Articles: 56
- Viewers: 266
- Followers: 58
- Page Flips: 256

Figure 14: HIT2GAP Flipboard activity (Articles, Followers and Viewers) from Sep 2016 to Aug 2019

4.4 Twitter HIT2GAP account activity Report

Twitter is a leader internet based social network that allows short messages of 140 characters. Its popularity has grown since it was first launched in 2006 and nowadays can be accessed by more than 100 million users worldwide. HIT2GAP twitter account address is <https://twitter.com/HIT2GAP>, while the @HIT2GAP username is used in twitter mobile phone apps. Figure 15 shows a screenshot of the HIT2GAP account feed latest tweets.

Figure 15: Twitter HIT2GAP account

The HIT2GAP twitter account was created on 6th November 2015. Since then, **117 tweets** were written from the account with a significant number of tweets being favoured and retweeted. A total of **98507 impressions** have been made by the HIT2GAP tweets, most of them were organic. One only tweet has been promoted and reached 18,477 impressions. This means that HIT2GAP tweets have been viewed more than 98,000 people in total. The tweets have generated also 5392 profile visits and the @hit2gap account has been mentioned 228 times. The account has **317 followers**.

The top tweet in the first reporting period with 838 impressions was a general tweet announcing the release of the project public reports, made on the 13th Feb 2017. The top mention with 79 engagements, was made by @stephengarvin70, the 22nd Nov 2016, regarding one of the filmclips produced for HIT2GAP. Figure 16 shows the top tweet and top mention, and Figure 19 shows a summary graph of the HIT2GAP tweeter account data aggregated by month.

Figure 16: Reporting Period 1 – Top Tweet (left) and Top Tweet Mention (right)

For the Reporting period 2 the top tweets and organic impressions have been growing significantly, as an example, the top-earning impressions tweet was in May 2018 with **1267 impressions** (see Figure 17 below).

Figure 17: Reporting Period 2 Top tweet

Regarding Reporting Period 3, Figure 18 below shows the most relevant activity. The Top mention tweet earned 43 engagements and was produced by UDG highlighting a talk by Dr. Joaquim Melendez (UdG) where he presented the Hit2Gap approach among other projects.

The Top Tweet was the promotional one of the final event in Galway “The Future of Building Energy Management” that earned 1354 impressions. This tweet was a promoted tweet.

Regarding BEMServer, the top tweet was by Pierre Bourreau (NBK) where he announced the online release of the new portal. This tweet earned 26 engagements.

Top mention earned 43 engagements

eXiT- Research Group_UdG
@eXIT_UdG · Mar 12

El Dr. Joaquim Meléndez (@QuimMF) presentant ""BIZLINE: Eines per la #monitorització i optimització energètica".

Referència els projectes @HIT2GAP, @RESOLVD_EU i @elandh2020.
pic.twitter.com/UEfFqKCe1H

Top Tweet earned 1,384 impressions

Join us to discuss THE FUTURE of BUILDING ENERGY MANAGEMENT.

ONLINE broadcast here:
[app.vscene.net/webcastportal/...](http://app.vscene.net/webcastportal/)
Register here:
eventbrite.ie/e/the-future-o...

#energyefficiency #buildingsimulation
#EnergyTransition #FacilitiesMgmt
#openaccess #H2020
pic.twitter.com/N3ag09Y14F

4 7

View Tweet activity

View all Tweet activity

Top mention earned 26 engagements

Pierre Bourreau
@BourreauPierre · Aug 12

Now online! The code of #BEMServer is available on Github.
linkedin.com/posts/bemserve...
@HIT2GAP @NobatekInef4

5 6

View Tweet

Figure 18 - Reporting Period 3 twitter highlights

The graphs below summarize the activity (No. of Tweets, Tweet Impress, Mentions and New Followers) of @HIT2GAP twitter account from November 2015 till August 2019.

Figure 19: Summary graph of the HIT2GAP tweeter account data aggregated by month

4.5 Promotional Video Material

Two promotional videos were produced in the 1st period. The first one is a cartoon-style filmclip about the behaviour module. It was produced through Apintech and was posted on the HIT2GAP website in 2016. The aim of the behaviour modules is to deliver user behaviour information to the building users, to highlight energy wastage and to suggest behavioural and systemic changes. The video is available in the HIT2GAP webpage. <http://www.hit2gap.eu/about-the-project/hit2gap-modules>. Screenshots are shown in Figure 20 and Figure 21, below.

Figure 20: HIT2GAP Behaviour Module video screenshots

<p>EVENTS TO BE MONITORED (EXAMPLES)</p> <p>Event No 1</p> <p>lighting on under no occupancy/presence</p> <p>Outputs</p> <p>Communication of waste impact</p> <p>Notification to shut off lights</p>	<p>EVENTS TO BE MONITORED (EXAMPLES)</p> <p>Event No 2</p> <p>high indoor temperatures (in winter) with no occupancy/ presence</p> <p>OR</p>
<p>EVENTS TO BE MONITORED (EXAMPLES)</p> <p>Event No 2</p> <p>low indoor temperatures (in summer) with no user presence</p>	<p>EVENTS TO BE MONITORED (EXAMPLES)</p> <p>Event No 2</p> <p>Outputs</p> <p>Communication of waste impact</p> <p>Notification to change thermostats</p> <p>Evaluation of the Impact of using multiple thermostat set points taking account of user presence</p>
<p>EVENTS TO BE MONITORED (EXAMPLES)</p> <p>Event No 3</p> <p>heating/ cooling losses due to an "open window" event</p>	<p>EVENTS TO BE MONITORED (EXAMPLES)</p> <p>Event No 3</p> <p>Outputs</p> <p>Communication of waste impact</p> <p>Notify user about the event</p>
<p>EVENTS TO BE MONITORED (EXAMPLES)</p> <p>Event No 4</p> <p>high CO₂ / dust levels</p>	<p>EVENTS TO BE MONITORED (EXAMPLES)</p> <p>Event No 4</p> <p>Outputs</p> <p>Notification of event</p>

Figure 21: HIT2GAP Behaviour Module video screenshots

The second video is a film clip made using student actors, a screenshot of this video is shown in Figure 22. The clip is a narrative story involving different stakeholders involved in a energy review of a building where they are briefed about innovative control technology developed within HIT2GAP. This video was shown internally to all HIT2GAP partners and is currently undergoing further revision.

Figure 22: HIT2GAP Promotional video produced at BRE

A third video more product-oriented has been produced during the 3rd period of the project (<https://youtu.be/fbamTkjYg50>).

Figure 23: Screenshot of the BEMServer video

4.6 YouTube HIT2GAP Channel

Eight videos were produced by the CELTS service at NUIG. Project participants answered a number of questions such as: (1) Present yourself and your organizations role, (2) What is the role of your organization in HIT2GAP? (3) What is the most challenging part of HIT2GAP for your organization? HIT2GAP Youtube channel are available to the public (see link below). The videos were produced and tagged as “Intelligent buildings and HIT2GAP technology“ (see below Figure 24):

- Jessica Mouawad (Bouyges Energies & Services) – [French](#)
- Jessica Mouawad (Bouyges Energies & Services) – [English](#)
- Dr. Joaquim Melendez (University of Girona) – [Catalan](#)
- Dr. Joaquim Melendez (University of Girona) – [Spanish](#)
- Nikos Sakkas (Apintech Ltd. / POLIS-21 Ltd) – [English](#)
- Luis M. Blanes (National University of Ireland Galway) – [English](#)
- Gorka Naveran Lanz (Giroa-Veolia) – [Spanish](#)
- Pascale Brassier (NOBATEK) – [French](#)

Figure 24: HIT2GAP Youtube channel. Available from https://www.youtube.com/channel/UChbVGaWjNSnCTN9SciHpv_A/videos.

The statistics for viewing the project’s videos are as follows:

	+	Impressions	Impressions click-through rate	Views ↓	Average view duration	Watch time (minutes)
Total		433	4.8%	146 100.0%	1:10	172 100.0%
BEMServer Making sense of your building data		24	12.5%	53 36.3%	1:33	83 48.2%
Jessica Mouawad, Bouygues Energies & Services – Bâtiments intel...		77	6.5%	26 17.8%	0:49	22 12.5%
BEMServer Making sense of your building data update		15	26.7%	17 11.6%	0:43	12 7.1%
Jessica Mouawad of Bouygues Energies & Services		117	2.6%	14 9.6%	1:13	17 9.9%
Pascale Brassier-NOBATEK, La Solution HIT2GAP au service des b...		24	4.2%	14 9.6%	1:28	21 12.0%
Gorka Naveran Lanz-de Giroa-Veolia – Edificios inteligentes y tecno...		37	5.4%	7 4.8%	0:26	3 1.8%
Nikos Sakkas of Apintech Ltd / POLIS-21 Ltd - Intelligent buildings ...		41	0.0%	6 4.1%	1:41	10 5.9%
Luis M Blanes-of IRUSE/Galway – Intelligent buildings and HIT2GA...		34	5.9%	4 2.7%	0:46	3 1.8%
Dr Joaquim Melendez-Universidad de Girona – Edificios inteligente...		38	2.6%	3 2.1%	0:08	0 0.3%
Dr Joaquim Melendez Universitat de Girona – Edificios intel-ligents i ...		26	0.0%	2 1.4%	0:23	1 0.5%

(source: YouTube stats)

4.7 LinkedIn HIT2GAP group

A LinkedIn page was launched in March 2018. LinkedIn is the most valued professional network worldwide. It's followed by 40 members.

The screenshot shows the LinkedIn group page for HIT2GAP. The group name is "HIT2GAP - Highly Innovative Building Controls – Tackling the Energy Performance Gap". It is a standard group with 40 members. The group is led by Lori McElroy, Director - Housing and Energy (Scotland) at BRE (Building Research Establishment). The group's purpose is to allow project partners to share information and receive feedback. A recent post by Lori McElroy, dated 1 week ago, mentions that the BEMServer promotional video is now ready and available on EMDESK. The video thumbnail shows a diagram of the BEMServer API and BEMServer components. The page also features a "Promoted" section with two ads: "Are you a PM?" and "Lakers Mobile Cafe".

Figure 25: HIT2GAP LinkedIn page

4.8 Instagram HIT2GAP account

Instagram account was launched also during 2018. This is seen as a particular interesting option to exchange pictures and graphical material of the project.

Figure 26: HIT2GAP Instagram account

4.9 BEMServer Website

A Website dedicated to BEMServer has been created during RP3 corresponding to the launch of BEMServer during the BIM World 2019 exhibition. It is accessible from <https://www.bemserver.org/> (see figure below).

BEMServer Making sense of your building data

What is BEMServer?

BEMServer is an open source solution for data-driven, modular, scalable and secure building energy management system.

Using the most advanced web technologies, **your building data gain meaning to empower all building actors**, from managers to occupants, with new services to optimize energy consumption.

Up to
25%
energy savings

What you can do with BEMServer

Facility Managers	Module Developers	Contributors
<p>Collect all your data at one central location. With data, insights and reports, you can optimize data-driven energy consumption.</p>	<p>Extend what you know, adding new data and functionality to your stack.</p>	<p>Get data, fully tested and managed code, and go part in an open source project, to build up the solution you want.</p>
<p>Choose the right module that fits to your needs to avoid you or your daily job.</p>	<p>Use (existing) data and do not waste time, reviewing what are the data sources, building the right data model, and integrating it with the rest of the system.</p>	<p>Provide an architectural building monitoring and your best proposals.</p>
Your energy monitoring solution	Your backbone solution	The place to join forces

The end result is the world's first open source community and platform dedicated to building performance and reducing the energy gap.

For more information, contact us

- 1 Choose the right module that fits to your needs to avoid you or your daily job.
- 2 It processes and makes the resulting data available through a documented API.
- 3 Modules use dataset to implement actions, recommendations and controls.
- 4 Information is delivered to energy managers, building owners and/or occupants.

Figure 27: BEMServer One Page website

During the period April 2019 to 12 September 2019, the number of users increased to 614. Over this period, there were 1100 sessions and 1585 page views, giving an average of 1.44 pages per session - approximately 290 page views per month. The average duration of each session was 1 minute and 13 seconds. On average, there were 1.79 visits per user, indicating that a significant number of people have revisited the site. The top country for visits to the BEMServer website was France (500 sessions), followed by Turkey (66 sessions), the United States (61 sessions) and Spain (59 sessions).

Figure 28: BEMServer website statistics

Pays ?	Acquisition			Comportement		
	Utilisateurs ? ↓	Nouveaux utilisateurs ?	Sessions ?	Taux de rebond ?	Pages/session ?	Durée moyenne des sessions ?
	616 % du total: 100,00 % (616)	616 % du total: 100,16 % (615)	1103 % du total: 100,00 % (1103)	81,96 % Valeur moy. pour la vue: 81,96 % (0,00 %)	1,45 Valeur moy. pour la vue: 1,45 (0,00 %)	00:01:13 Valeur moy. pour la vue: 00:01:13 (0,00 %)
1. France	201 (31,96 %)	198 (32,14 %)	500 (45,33 %)	82,40 %	1,51	00:01:27
2. United States	53 (8,43 %)	53 (8,60 %)	61 (5,53 %)	85,25 %	1,34	00:01:48
3. Spain	47 (7,47 %)	45 (7,31 %)	59 (5,35 %)	86,44 %	1,22	00:00:48
4. Turkey	31 (4,93 %)	31 (5,03 %)	66 (5,98 %)	86,36 %	1,15	00:01:05
5. Italy	30 (4,77 %)	29 (4,71 %)	57 (5,17 %)	82,46 %	1,18	00:00:57
6. India	26 (4,13 %)	26 (4,22 %)	30 (2,72 %)	70,00 %	1,67	00:01:22
7. Germany	25 (3,97 %)	24 (3,90 %)	33 (2,99 %)	75,76 %	1,97	00:01:14
8. United Kingdom	25 (3,97 %)	23 (3,73 %)	49 (4,44 %)	69,39 %	1,73	00:01:41
9. Ireland	24 (3,82 %)	24 (3,90 %)	40 (3,63 %)	85,00 %	1,32	00:00:19
10. China	12 (1,91 %)	9 (1,46 %)	12 (1,09 %)	91,67 %	1,50	00:00:17

Figure 29: Statistics for visits to BEMServer website by country

4.10 BEMServer LinkedIn

A LinkedIn page was launched in March 2019.

Figure 30: BEMServer LinkedIn page

4.11 BEMServer Storyboard

A storyboard has been developed during RP3. It aims at being used during a commercial presentation to a potential client detailing different use cases and explaining the benefits get from using the solution.

Figure 31: BEMServer storyboard

5 COMPENDIUM

A summary of the number of Dissemination and Awareness Activities (D&A) and an estimated reach audience to date is shown in Table 3. This summary reflects the activities from the beginning till the end of the project (M1-M48). The total figures are approximated.

Criteria for the estimation of dissemination reach:

- Scientific Journal Publications account for both peer-reviewed and non-peer reviewed publications that are indexed in a periodic Journal publications. The reach number is based in the ELSEVIER “captures”, number of citations and number of downloads;
- Scientific Conference Participations account for all participations in conferences. Reach is estimated on number of attendees to the session where the communication was presented;
- EU Research events are EU-Sponsored brokerage and ECTP conferences;
- Workshop, Exhibitions, Fairs and Industry conferences are the rest of dissemination actions in Section 2.2.1)
- Social Media Communications. With regards to the reach of social media, we accounted for final engagements with tweets, posts etc,. Impressions (times a tweet is shown in a device) are not accounted for.
- Mass Media communications account for Presse Releases (ARTICLE in 2.2.1 Section), the reach was estimated by 250 person average.
- Newsletter reach are measured by the total number of people who opened the letters (only counted once).

Table 3 – Compendium of D&A Activities

D&A Activities type	ACTIONS	Reach
Scientific – Journal Publications	9	2,448
Scientific – Conference Participations	22	3,220
EU research events	4	430
Workshops, Exhibitions, Fairs, Industry conferences	63	6,711
Social Media Communications (Flipboard, Web, Twitter)	183	11,385
Mass Media Communications (TV, Radio, Press)	6	1,500
Newsletters	6	523
TOTAL ACTIONS	293	26,217

6 Acronyms and abbreviations

ABO	ABO Data
API	APINTECH
BES	Bouygues Energies & Services
BPS	Building Performance Simulation
BRE	Building Research Establishment
CA	Consortium Agreement
CYL	CYLON
CYR	Cyric
DOA	Description of the action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
D&A	Dissemination and Awareness
EC	European Commission
EGE	Ege University
EM	Exploitation manager
ENE	Enerit Ltd.
EU	European Union
EUR	EURECAT
EVO	Evolution
FISE	Fraunhofer ISE
GA	Grant Agreement
GIR	GIROA
H2020	Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
LIU	LIUPPA Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour
NBK	Nobatek
NUIG	National University of Ireland, Galway
NSF	National Stakeholder Forum
MOS	Mostostal
R2M	R2M Solutions
SC	Steering Committee
TEK	IK4-TEKNIKER
TL	Task Leader
UDG	University of Girona
UOS	University of Strathclyde
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
WRS	City of Warsaw
ZUT	Zutec

7 ANNEX 1 – Action type

WS-IN	Workshop – Industry
WS-PB	Workshop – Professional Body
WS-AC	Workshop – Academic
CPD	Continuous Professional Development
PEV	Partner Events
UPEV	Unique Partner Event
TES	Testimonials
SHF	Stakeholders Forum
CONF	Conference
SEM	Seminar
EU-EEB	Energy Efficient Building Platform events (Build Up – ECTPC, PLEA, etc.)
INEF4	INEF 4 event
EDU	Training and Education Event
H2020	H2020 event
ARTICLE	Article in a Trade Journal, Interest Groups Magazine or Non-Scientific Journals
INDEX	Indexing in Networking databases. Mention in Industry or Research Reports
EXH	Exhibition

8 ANNEX 2 – Audience Type

PP	Project Participants
PB	Professional Bodies
G-L	Government – Local
G-N	Government – National
G-EN	Government Energy Agencies
RFA	Research Funding Agency
FI	Financial Institutions
I-BMS	Industry BMS provider, Control Systems
I-SW	Industry - Software Development Companies
I-ESCO	Energy Services Contractors
HEI	Higher Education Institutions. (Universities, Institutes of Technology, Vocational)
RI	Research Institutions
PB-AR	Professional Body - Architecture
PB-EN	Professional Body - Engineering
PB-IT	Professional Body – Information Technology
PB-CM	Professional Body - Construction
PB-BS	Professional Body – Building Services
I-GC	Industry – General Contractors
I-RE	Industry – Real Estate Management Companies
P-FM	Professional – Facility Managers
P-EM	Professionals – Energy Managers
EU-H2020	H2020 project participants
CON	Consumer support body

9 ANNEX 3 – Logo, leaflet and poster developed during RP3

BEMServer

Powered by hit2gap

The World's premier open source Building Energy Management Platform

BEMServer is an open source solution to deploy a modular, scalable and secure Building Energy Management System. Using the most advanced web technologies, your building data gain meaning to empower all building actors, from managers to occupants, with new services to optimize energy consumption.

Your building data make sense

BEMServer includes data treatment modules developed by the HIT2GAP project partners:

- Load forecasting
- Fault detection and diagnosis (2 modules)
- User behaviour (2 modules)
- Energy management
- Building performance simulation (2 modules)
- Calibration
- Gap reasoning
- Renewable energy simulation
- Visualisation

HIT2GAP project Partners

For more information please contact the team

contact@bemserver.org

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 680708.

hit2gap

www.hit2gap.eu

Highly Innovative building control Tools Tackling the energy performance GAP

Purpose

Differences between expected and actual energy consumptions in buildings appear from issues arising from the design, construction, commissioning and operation. This **Energy Performance GAP**, which often exceeds 50% of the overall energy consumption, has detrimental implications for the achievement of EU energy targets.

The objective of the HIT2GAP project is:

- to reduce the energy performance gap between predicted and actual building performance, focusing on the **operational phase of buildings**;
- to propose a **new paradigm** for the development of **energy management platforms in buildings**, integrating existing expertise and resources;
- to provide a **smart, open platform** associated with **added value modules based on analysis** of data collected in the building.

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, HIT2GAP is active from September 2015 to August 2019.

Project partners

Solution developed

www.bemserver.org

MODULES

SYSTEM MONITORING

- Fault Detection & Diagnosis (PCA) by University of Orlans
- RealSIM - Renewable Energy Simulation Module by CyREC
- Rule-Based Fault Detection & Diagnosis by Fraunhofer ISE

ENERGY CONTROL

- Energy Management by Enerit
- Load Forecasting by University of Orlans
- GasReasoner by Fraunhofer ISE
- MCGCC - Reduced Order Models to tackle the performance gap by National University of Ireland Galway
- Indoor Environmental Quality by University of Strathclyde

ENERGY BEHAVIOUR

- Semantic-driven Behaviour Simulation by Edge University
- WT-Behave by ARINTECH LTD

VISUALIZATION

- Facility Management Visualization by Fraunhofer ISE
- Energy Management Visualization by Enerit
- MyEnergyAssistant by Inrova
- BIM Visualization by Z.I.A.C.

Targets

End-users/customers:

- Building Owner, Estate Manager
- Energy Manager / Facility Manager / Maintenance Manager (EPC, awareness raising of occupants)
- ESCo / Facility Management organisations
- Energy Efficiency Consultant/ Professional (e.g. engineers, designers)
- BMS providers (to enrich the existing offer).

Contributors (win-win strategy):

- External module developers
- Actors in the value chain associated with monitoring and measurement of building energy performance
- Open source community

Key benefits

- Save energy by detecting bad functioning of systems or energy waste
- Detect abnormal energy consumption and its location
- Improve your own existing services (linked to commissioning for instance)
- Improve maintenance activities
- Increase indoor comfort conditions for the occupants
- Decrease occupants' complaints rate
- Save time in your day-to-day job

Contact details

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Find us on:

- www.hit2gap.eu
- www.bemserver.org
- [@HIT2GAP](https://www.instagram.com/hit2gap/)
- <https://www.instagram.com/hit2gap/>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12009520>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/hit2gap/>

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